

Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024

Workshop Proceedings

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Editorial

This volume contains the abstracts of the talks and posters from the Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024 (DSgG 2024) workshop. The workshop is part of an annual workshop series organized by the Research Data Management Working Group of TU9 (Alliance of leading Technical Universities in Germany). The DSgG workshop series provides a platform for direct interaction within the Research Data Management (RDM) community. It brings together data stewards, research data officers, research software engineers, data experts, data curators, and data managers to share insights about their professional experiences and explore current development trends in Germany and beyond. Additionally, these workshops function as a forum for showcasing innovative solutions, addressing pressing challenges, and delivering thorough evaluations in the field of data stewardship.

The workshop took place from September 11 to 12, 2024 at the SuperC in Aachen¹ and was mainly organized by the RWTH Aachen University Library and the local RDM team. After the last two workshops in Braunschweig and Dresden, this year's workshop was attended by more than 70 people.

After last year's DSgG in Dresden, the theme of which was "Collective exploration of the increasingly established concept of data stewardship", this year's theme "Community building for data stewardship", this year's theme was "Community building for data stewardship". In order to approach this topic systematically, the workshop used the Community Canvas², which has already been used successfully in Flanders. In her key note, Paula Garcia Oset from Ghent University presented how the Community Canvas was used in Flanders³, what the results were and what conclusions and activities followed from the results.

After the key note, the program started by including over the two days nine talks, three poster sessions with 28 posters and three group work phases on the Community Canvas. During the group work phases, six groups addressed the different sections of the Community Canvas - identity, experiences and structure. The groups analyzed the different aspects of the sections, i.e. for the identity section, such as member identity, definition of success, values, ... In general, two groups each covered almost all aspects. The results were documented and analysed. The results will be presented at an online event in November 2024. Furthermore, attention was paid to ensuring that there was sufficient time for exchange and networking to take up the idea of community building again.

Thank you for the numerous fascinating contributions that significantly enhanced the success of the event. The next Data Stewardship goes Germany workshop will be held in Karlsruhe in 2025. More details will be announced soon.

In addition to the DSgG, two satellite events were offered. From Thursday afternoon to Friday noon, 17 participants took part in the 8-hour satellite event *Fundamentals of Scientific Metadata: Why Context Matters* offered by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration. In parallel,

¹ <https://www.dsgg.rwth-aachen.de/cms/~bgnhzs/dsgg/>

² <https://community-canvas.org/>

³ Oset García, P. (2024, September 17). Building a community of data stewards in Flanders - The FRDN Knowledge Hub's experience with the Community Canvas. Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024 (DSgG 2024), Aachen. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13773134>

on Thursday afternoon, the 4-hour event on *The Heliocentric Model of Open Science - Literature Content Management* offered by the Forschungszentrum Jülich, in which 12 people participated.

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Becoming domain-specific experts – potentials of research data management within a priority program

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Introduction

Research data management (RDM) has become a core aspect of research, especially since the establishment of the FAIR-Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016) and comprehensive infrastructure projects, e.g. the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)⁴ (Hartl, Wössner and Sure-Vetter 2021). Besides several helpdesk services of the NFDI consortia, Universities have founded local generic RDM counseling units and domain-specific RDM centers as primary facilities that support researchers in questions regarding RDM and offer RDM (infrastructure) services.⁵

However, large research programs (such as collaborative research centers and transregios, research training groups, excellence clusters and priority programs) often organize their RDM independently of these RDM centers through designated staff. Core aspects of this self-managed RDM are a profound knowledge of domain-specific RDM requirements and the cooperation with different stakeholders and RDM networks, like computing centers and infrastructure projects.

In our talk, we will present the RDM unit of the priority program SPP 2207 “Computational Literary Studies”⁶ (Pielström and Jung 2022) funded by the

German Research Foundation (DFG). We will focus on approaches of measuring RDM requirement landscapes, how our work helped us identify domain-specific RDM requirements and address them together with other RDM infrastructures and initiatives.

Research Data Management in the Priority Program SPP 2207

The Priority Program

Currently, the priority program SPP 2207 is in its second funding phase. During its first funding period, the program consisted of ten distributed research projects in two countries. At present, eight distributed research projects are funded. Additionally, in both periods a central project has been responsible for the management of the program as well as for the development and establishment of a common RDM strategy for the funded projects.

RDM during the first funding period

For developing a common RDM strategy for the whole priority program, it was central to evaluate the state of the art regarding research and RDM of the ten distributed research projects of the program (Helling, Jung and Pielström 2021). Therefore, we did several qualitative interviews (Helling et al. 2020) with participants of all research projects. These interviews were structured

⁴ <https://www.nfdi.de/>, (last access: 13th May 2024).

⁵ <https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/FDM-Kontakte>, (last access: 13th May 2024).

⁶ <https://dfg-spp-cls.github.io/>, (last access: 2nd July 2024).

by interview guidelines with five main topics:

Working with research data

- Daily work with research data e.g., the use of programming languages, tools, scientific methods;
- What kind of data is used within the research project e.g., datatypes and -formats, representation layers;

Research data management in the research project

- Collaboration within the research projects e.g., the organization of data exchange between project members and the use of collaborative storage infrastructure;
- Used data storage within the research projects e.g., the use of specific storage infrastructure, backup strategies;

Development of living systems⁷

- Information about living systems e.g., the type and function of living systems, use of technology-stacks;

Research data management at the end of the research project

- Archiving research data e.g., what data needs to be archived, the use of infrastructures for archiving research data;
- Publishing research data e.g., what data will be published, the use of infrastructures for publishing research data;

Handling living systems at the end of the research project

- Hosting living systems e.g., where the living system will be hosted, who is

⁷ Dynamic environments, access points to data, representation forms of data that need to be curated permanently. Core functionality of living systems is to ensure accessibility and reusability of research data in a specific form.

⁸ <https://about.gitlab.com/>, (last access: 13th May 2024).

responsible for the long term hosting of the living system;

The results of these qualitative interviews allowed us to develop a comprehensive RDM profile for the research field of the priority program and to identify specific RDM requirements of the research projects (Jung, Helling and Pielström 2023). In addition, it helped us gain more knowledge about the specific research field of the program (Helling, Jung and Pielström 2022a).

On this basis, we set up a common Gitlab⁸ for the program to allow collaborative work, a central instance of Mattermost⁹ and we developed a research data management strategy for storing, archiving and publishing research results of the program. This includes not only a Zenodo¹⁰ community for publications related to the program, but also a comprehensive achievements list on the website of the program and a Zotero library (Helling, Jung and Pielström 2022b).¹¹

RDM during the second funding period

Within the second funding period, the knowledge about the RDM landscape of the priority program was used for developing a domain-specific research data management plan (DMP). This plan works as a domain data protocol (DDP)¹² (Eckert and Netscher 2021; Science Europe 2018) for the research field of the program (Jung,

⁹ <https://mattermost.com/>, (last access: 13th May 2024).

¹⁰ https://zenodo.org/communities/spp_cls/, (last access: 13th May 2024).

¹¹ https://www.zotero.org/groups/4667571/spp_cls-achievements, (last access: 13th May 2024).

¹² See also: standardized data management plans for educational research (Stamp), <https://www.forschungsdaten-bildung.de/stamp-nutzen>, (last access: 13th of May 2024).

Helling and Pielström 2024).¹³ Its structure is based on the design of generic DMPs with domain-specific supplements. For every aspect of RDM, the DDP offers domain-specific options in a multiple-choice form. These options are based on the results of the qualitative interviews from the first funding period. The DDP for the priority program is implemented in an instance of the Research Data Management Organizer (RDMO),¹⁴ hosted by the central project of the program. The data model of the DDP will be published for reuse after the program ends.

Collaboration with the (inter)national RDM community

Besides the development of a comprehensive RDM strategy for the priority program, a core task of the central project is the improvement of RDM for the research field of the program. To achieve this goal, all results of the research on RDM obtained by the central project were published open access and were presented and discussed at different (inter)national RDM workshops and discipline-specific conferences. In addition, we are working closely with other (inter)national infrastructures and research projects to address domain-specific requirements regarding RDM. Together with the Consortium Text+¹⁵ from the National German Research Infrastructure (NFDI)¹⁶ and the international domain-specific infrastructure project CLSInfra¹⁷, we carried out a quantitative survey on domain-specific metadata requirements of our research community (Calvo Tello et al. 2024) and worked together with partner

networks on improving a domain-specific repository.

Conclusion

Due to the heterogeneity of research and RDM requirements, we are convinced that RDM needs to be as domain specific as possible. Priority programs and other larger research programs are very often a blueprint of specific research communities and so they lend themselves well to analyses of and investigations on RDM from a domain-specific perspective, as we have hopefully shown in this paper.

In our talk, we will describe the possibilities of doing research on domain-specific RDM in the context of the priority program SPP 2207 more in detail. In addition, we will argue for the necessity of collaboration with other stakeholders in RDM, to address RDM requirements in a comprehensive way.

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¹³ <https://cls-rdmo.phil.uni-wuerzburg.de/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

¹⁴ <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/>, (last access: 13th of May 2024).

¹⁵ <https://text-plus.org/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

¹⁶ <https://www.nfdi.de/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

¹⁷ <https://clsinfra.io/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

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Support research data management in health studies: library and research working together in a data steward pilot

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This pilot project within a medicine-oriented consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI4Health) aims to explore the impact of two library-based data stewards working closely together with people who conduct(ed) health studies and to serve as a positive practical example for other libraries or infrastructure institutions wishing to establish data stewardship together with discipline specific research projects. It also aims to explore the relationship between generic research data management (RDM) knowledge at library or infrastructure level as well as for various disciplines within a research institution, and to then determine how this knowledge can be combined to benefit both¹⁸.

Regarding the tasks and embedding of data stewards, the so-called embedded or discipline-specific data steward comes into play. In addition to general issues of research data management, these individuals are primarily concerned with the specific tasks associated with their particular discipline. This involves managing medical research data, primarily from clinical and epidemiological studies. The profiles of a discipline-specific data steward and an infrastructure-related data steward are based on the profiles

developed as part of the 'DataStew' project, in which five profiles for data stewardship were derived based on areas of expertise and training opportunities¹⁹.

The pilot project describes the initial situation, the roles of data stewards on both infrastructure and research levels, the goals of collaboration between the two, and the approach taken. The experiences gleaned by the two libraries implementing a data steward for epidemiological and a data steward for clinical studies will be illustrated and the main features of the two approaches will be given.

The initial situation is characterised by the different expertise of the infrastructure and discipline specific data stewards: the expertise in the libraries comprises basic research data management concepts like the FAIR data principles or metadata. Further, they are involved in the development of standards within the NFDI consortium, e.g. a publication guideline, a metadata schema for data publication or templates for data management plans. Discipline-specific data stewards from research, on the other hand, have less experience with generic RDM, but bring discipline-specific expertise, either from

¹⁸ Fürst, J., Dierkes, J., Lindstädt, B., Perrar, I., & Shutsko, A. (2024). Demonstrator of the Data Stewardship Service. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006483497>

¹⁹ Eva Seidlmayer, Fabian Hoffmann, Jens Dierkes, Birte Lindstädt, Ralf Depping, Konrad U. Förstner:

[Forschung unterstützen - Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen : Ergebnisse des Projektes DataStew](#), 2023, DOI 10.4126/FRL01-006441397, page 72 ff

epidemiological or clinical research, when it comes to methods and workflows. They assessed the RDM in place for the studies conducted by their research institute, highlighting which RDM strategy was already in place and which other parts of RDM were missing.

Additionally, their role involves testing the established standards and services, as well as soliciting feedback from research and the broader research community for the relevant study.

This pilot aims to combine the knowledge of the infrastructure provider and the research party. The initial aim was for both to familiarise themselves with and gain a thorough understanding of each other's perspective. The infrastructure data steward would collaborate with the researcher or discipline-specific data steward to design an infrastructure that caters to the needs of the researchers at their institution. The discipline-specific data steward, being well-versed with the specific requirements of the researchers, offers valuable input on the necessary infrastructure. The two data stewards then jointly develop training formats covering basic RDM concepts and consortium specific services, such as a central search hub (CSH). The aim was to educate researchers on RDM in general, but especially on data publication, e.g. equip them with the knowledge needed to input their studies (= study metadata) into the CSH.

An important result of the pilot involving two use cases of different study types was that it is essential to find the right contact person involved with research. While in the epidemiological study it was clear from the outset that a person within the study would be selected as a counterpart to the data steward, it proved difficult to find the right contact person (counterpart) for the partner „clinical trial center“. The main reason for this is that a clinical trial center is a service provider or infrastructure partner like the library, although with different service portfolios.

As an overall result it is evident that both data steward profiles are necessary, because synergy effects are created through their cooperation. The extent to which fundamental knowledge, can be merged into one individual in the future relies on the availability of training opportunities. One option could be to provide training for researchers in the role of a data steward on the fundamentals of RDM. This could be accomplished through a certification course akin to the one presently available in North Rhine-Westphalia.

It seems more difficult to train a generic data steward in the basics of a discipline, as this would require at least a bachelor's degree in that discipline. Liaising between an infrastructure data steward and a research data steward therefore seems appropriate given the current situation.

Data steward networks through FAIR-IMPACT workshops and draft review to promote BonaRes Repository

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As a data infrastructure data steward with the BonaRes project, my responsibilities include enhancing the prominence of our data infrastructure, publishing data, educating researchers in research data management, and assisting them in ensuring their data is FAIR. Consequently, it has become crucial for me to establish connections with researchers, project leaders, fellow data stewards, data service providers, data users, and the wider scientific community. I set up a separate mailing list for all of the project principal investigators (PI) to facilitate networking and communication with the various 16 collaborative projects that must publish data in our data infrastructure, and I ensured that each PI assigned a researcher responsible for research data management (RDM) within their project. This allowed me to maintain touch with the focal researchers (16), who were then in charge of distributing RDM-related material from our team to the rest of the project members. Because some researchers still find RDM-related topics boring or secondary, receiving frequent emails in these areas turns them off and makes data stewards' aims even more difficult to achieve. One effective communication method at the institutional level was to target smaller working groups rather than organising

RDM events for the entire institute. Smaller groups allow for the discovery and solutions of specific requirements. My current

concentration is on early-career researchers, primarily PhDs and postdocs.

It's interesting to see how enthused these scholars are about RDM. Given that they handle the majority of the data collection, cleaning, and analysis, it is clear that networking with them will elevate RDM to new heights, and they may be able to persuade their superiors of the need of RDM.

To boost the exposure of our data infrastructure, we organise workshops on specific and broad RDM themes, and all training materials include links to significant documentations or repository-related websites. Networking through broad RDM subjects proved to be quite effective, as RDM stakeholders who were not interested in data publication were drawn to these broad topics and then got interested in data publication. To increase the use of our repository, we used an outreach technique known as "data of the month". Each month, we showcase a single dataset or data collection across local and social media channels. These highlights generally include the title, abstract, photos, and, most crucially, the author's name and download link. This method has substantially enhanced the network, increasing data downloads as well as the repository's and authors' exposure. We currently receive requests for data from a range of sources, as well as guidance on data organisation and publishing.

Through my interactions with authors during the data publication process, I have encountered a range of issues that they have in ensuring the FAIRness of their data. While seeking training resources on the FAIR principles, I explored the FAIRsFAIR website and gained valuable insights into their initiatives. The FAIRsFAIR zenodo community approved the slides I uploaded on the zenodo platform following my workshop. Subsequently, I have stayed informed on FAIR Data-related matters through this project and have started participating in the FAIR Implementation Workshops held by the FAIR-IMPACT EU project, which succeeded the FAIRsFAIR project. By participating in workshops and subscribing to newsletters, I learned about the FAIR-IMPACT Open calls for support. I applied for one of the support actions called "Recommendations for trustworthy and FAIR-enabling data repositories," which will take place from May to September 2024, and my application was successful.

One of the reasons I applied for the FAIR-IMPACT Support Action was to relate my experience fulfilling the requirements for a trustworthy repository. To enhance the transparency and confidence in repositories, participants in the support action were required to evaluate the FAIR-IMPACT guidelines and offer comments for the draft's improvement. Above all, participants could get direction and help to increase the transparency of information regarding their repository service. Thanks to the FAIR-IMPACT support action and FAIR Implementation Workshops, I was also able to demonstrate how, working with authors, we can identify ways to enhance the FAIRness of their data.

Networking and communication were crucial while applying for the repository's Core Trust Seal (CTS) certification, as a data steward. To prepare the application, our team had to review the 16

CoreTrustSeal-Requirements-2023-2025 and make the necessary contacts with other stakeholders and third parties to complete the application, which is still under review. Participating in the FAIR-IMPACT support action and FAIR Implementation Workshops provided me with a better understanding of the types of information that can help end users make informed decisions about whether a repository is FAIR-enabling and trustworthy, as well as how the guidelines' implementation can help facilitate discovery, provide context, and support data interoperability. In summation, I felt confident that I had played an important role in shaping the guidelines, and would be one of the draft writers. Once our data infrastructure gets certified, we will encourage journal managers to suggest it to authors and data creators as the next step in boosting networking and collaboration thereby increasing the visibility of our data infrastructure.

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Atemkeng, M. F. and Wibberg, D. (2024). Checking and increasing the visibility of your publications. Zenodo, 16 May. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11204269>

BonaRes Repository:
<https://maps.bonares.de/mapapps/resources/apps/bonares>

FAIRsFAIR Training materials:
<https://www.fairsfair.eu/fair-frameworks-training-programmes>

How to apply for the CTS:
<https://www.coretrustseal.org/apply/>

FAIR –IMPACT Support Action:
<https://fair-impact.eu/support-offer-3-recommendations-trustworthy-and-fair-enabling-data-repositories>

FAIR-IMPACT Implementation
Workshop: <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-implementation-workshops>

Rent a Data Steward - hands-on support for Thuringian research groups: concept meeting first insights

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Starting at the end of 2022, two new members joined the TKFDM network as Thuringian Data Stewards to support research groups at Thuringian universities with their individual RDM needs. Step-by-step improvements for existing workflows in the respective groups are being developed cooperatively.

In this contribution, the concept [1] (first presented in May 2023) is juxtaposed with first insights from the practical experience of the two data stewards in Thuringian research groups, which has now lasted a few months.

The "Thüringer Kompetenznetzwerk Forschungsdatenmanagement" (TKFDM) is a collaborative effort of research data management helpdesks and initiatives in Thuringia to provide support to researchers of all Thuringian universities.

Together with colleagues in the FDM-HAWK project (BMBF 16FDFH107A) at the universities of applied sciences in Thuringia, the TKFDM raises awareness and builds competence among researchers in research data management, offering various workshop and event formats.

Information and training events are conducted on all aspects of research data management, including coffee lectures, the annual online conference "Thüringer FDM-Tage" and other activities addressing researchers of all career stages and

ranging from introductory level to specialized topics.

In addition to the general RDM consultants at each university, the TKFDM now offers the possibility to "Rent a Data Steward" in its pilot project of the same name. The offer is open to any research group at a public university in Thuringia, including all universities of applied sciences.

In the project, research groups can request the assistance of one of the two data stewards to improve the handling of their research data. Over the agreed term, a data steward supports a research group with its individual RDM challenges. Step-by-step improvements for the existing workflows are cooperatively developed.

The overall goal of such a collaboration is a sustainable and long-term improvement of the groups' RDM. The approach is rather pragmatic than oriented on theoretical RDM ideals.

The subjects of the collaborations are determined by the specific needs of the researchers and range from an initial analysis of current RDM practices in the group to the documentation and publication of research data, from the selection and adaptation of the available storage infrastructure and strategy to the use of software tools.

As with the choice of topics, the methods of collaboration will be tailored to the needs of the researchers, e.g. adopting best practices, propagating available services and liaising with local IT staff and federated infrastructure services, conducting collaborative think & work sessions, or giving skill-up workshops, e.g. for software such as git or GitLab.

On the other hand, due to the temporary nature of the collaborations, the data stewards do not take on permanent responsibilities within the research group or hosting institution.

First insights from a few months of experience with the data steward collaborations described above include:

- The rather unique approach in Thuringia "2 for all" - two data stewards to support research groups in the entire federal state of Thuringia - has its own twist: the landscape in the universities that the two data stewards are confronted with is sometimes very diverse: local conditions (regarding IT infrastructure, e.g. storage conditions) often differ significantly.

Although the RDM helpdesks facilitate connections to local service providers wherever possible and the TKFDM network has done and continues to do a great deal of conciliation work, key information for each university has to be gathered and, in some cases, negotiated, people in charge have to be identified at each location, and communication with each local IT service has to be established.

- Exchange with IT infrastructure suppliers takes a much higher share of the overall project time than expected.

- It is sometimes very difficult to reach contact persons due to a lack of capacity among the service providers.

- An anticipated and important task in the portfolio of the data stewards is not only to

communicate the needs of the researchers to the services providing the IT infrastructure, but also to identify those services that should be provided centrally by the federal computing center (HS-ITZ). The data stewards are actively involved in the conception and establishment of new services, e.g. an electronic laboratory notebook (ELN) based on eLabFTW, which is currently set up as a central service for all Thuringian universities, or the soon-to-be launched Repository for Research Data in Thuringia (REFODAT).

- During conception phase, it was expected that collaborations would only take a few weeks, with the stewards being something like a temporary team member. In practice, appointments between the team and the data steward are usually much less frequent than expected, the intensity of the collaboration phase with the research teams is often lower, while collaborations take longer to be concluded, altogether.

- In order to ensure commitment to a common goal of improving the RDM of a group, there are some formal requirements for initiating a data steward collaboration. A request can only be made by a PI, a consensus on the importance of RDM for today's research has to be reached beforehand, to name just two examples. Nonetheless, structured exchanges on RDM are rarely on most researchers' calendars. As a result, research groups value meetings with data stewards even more as an opportunity to work on their data management at a fixed date and time.

- In some cases, the data stewards find solutions for the teams, but more often the role is similar to that of a 'sparring partner': providing input, asking lots of questions, facilitating, guiding and empowering groups to come to their own conclusions, to make their own decisions.

Additional information about the pilot programme "Rent a Data Steward" can be

found on our website
<https://forschungsdaten-thueringen.de/data-stewards-en.html>

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Establishing a research data management system at BAM: Challenges and approaches

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The Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM, federal institute for materials science and testing) contributes to the standardization efforts of research data in various domains of materials science and engineering. Since 2021, a research data management (RDM) system (*BAM Data Store*) is being established to enable central storage of (meta)data generated during the active phase of the data lifecycle and enable compliance with the FAIR principles²⁰.

Since May 2023, after a successful pilot phase, the departments of eScience and IT infrastructure started the institute-wide rollout with the aim of integrating newly generated research data from up to sixty scientific units over a period of three years.

In this abstract, we review the components required to develop an institutional RDM service. We list challenges and lessons learned over a year to prioritize tasks and identify resources needed for data stewardship to achieve adoption of the RDM system.

The *BAM Data Store*: an institutional RDM system based on openBIS software

At BAM, research, development, and technical services are conducted with high societal impact by a scientific staff of more than 1,000 employees. The *BAM Data Store* is based on openBIS^{21, 22}, an open-source RDM software developed at ETH Zurich (ETHZ) that includes plugins for the digital representation of laboratory inventory, and an ELN. The openBIS framework, allows for the storage of meta(data), and provides interfaces for the integration of data analysis. At BAM, three to four divisions are enrolled every four months. Data store stewards (DS) and users are trained to use the software and develop first implementations. Under the guidance of the DS and the division lead, all users are responsible for implementing the data store to store newly generated research data according to RDM best practices to generate self-describing and traceable data sets.

20 Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. *Sci. Data* 2016, 3 (1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

21 Barillari, C. et al. openBIS ELN-LIMS: An Open-Source Database for Academic Laboratories.

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Development of RDM Services

For the development of RDM services, eight components were previously listed²³. These are relevant before (1), during (2) or after (3) data collection (Fig 1). With the aim of listing challenges identified over the course of a year and sharing the approaches to establishing an institutional RDM system at BAM, we address the components relevant during data collection: “*Managing active data*” and “*Guidance, Training, and Support*”.

Figure 1. Components of RDM services: To support effective data management and sharing an institution needs a coherent strategy and appropriate services. The digital curation centre (DCC) listed eight components in the guide “How to develop RDM services”. These are relevant before (1), during (2) and after (3) data collection.

Challenges and approaches of developing RDM services

During one-year of training users in the RDM system (*BAM Data Store*), we identified challenges faced to develop the RDM service for supporting management of active data. The *BAM Data Store* is primarily set up to document and store data in the “*Collection*” phase of the Data life cycle. To manage data during “*Processing*” and “*Analysis*”, the system allows the integration of Jupyter Notebooks. As the

system is set up to preserve data with access restricted to institutional members, data preservation in external data repositories is encouraged. Table 1 lists the challenges posed for developing the *BAM Data Store* as an institutional RDM service. The current focus is on set the challenges that arise during data collection.

23 Jones, G. et al. How to develop research data management services – a guide for HEIs’. DCC How-to Guides. DCC How-to Guides.

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1. Managing active data

Active Data Management	Challenges	Approaches
Collect	Automatic data migration from measuring devices to the RDM system	1. Development of underlying software function (openBIS-Dropbox) 2. Support in writing scripts for data migration
Process	Standard documentation of data processing	4. Support and train the use of tools (Jupyter Notebooks and openRefine)
Analyze	Documentation of data analysis	5. Support and train the use of Jupyter Notebooks
Preserve	Standard preservation	6. Define workflows, support and train for the use of Gitlab and the preparation of data for export to external data repositories

Table 1. Challenges and Approaches of Establishing RDM services: Active data management covers all steps of the data lifecycle before the data is published. Four challenges and approaches for prioritising resources for training and support are listed.

2. Guidance, Training and Support

The training and support concept was developed in 2023 to enable researchers to become Domain Data Stewards (DDS) with the aim of introducing the institutional groups to a centralised RDM system while ensuring adoption of the tool ⁵. The onboarding concept was tested for one year with seven groups identifying different levels of implementation in each group. We identified two main challenges for the implementation of the RDM system and thus for its development as a service: 1. the time needed by the DDS to customise the system, define and coordinate the RDM processes within the team. 2. the different levels of knowledge about concepts for the digital representation of data and data modeling. Although these concepts are more intuitive for researchers with strong programming background, communication between colleagues in multi-disciplinary contexts remains a challenge. To overcome these challenges, the concept was further developed before a new onboarding phase began in 2024. The challenges and approaches in terms of "guidance, training and support" are listed in Table 2 for four strategic steps for the implementation of the

RDM system based on the openBIS software.

We have started with an overarching strategy to guide data modeling workflow and improve implementation. For this, we introduced a new training module for "Data Model" and defined a successful onboarding phase as the one in which the DDS implements a use case. We also motivate this work by making it visible through the publication of data models and use cases. This process is supported by defining a publishing workflow, setting up an institutional GitLab repository and providing guidelines to make these datasets citable and reusable.

Strategic steps	Challenges	Approaches
Data Model	Mapping research data and related workflows in RDM software	7. Add training module – Data Model. Includes a data model guideline and supporting videos with use cases
Masterdata	Identify elements of the research processes that should be represented as entities and coordinate teamwork for iterative metadata development	8. Provide a collaborative tool to guide the team in identifying masterdata elements.
RDM system customization	Strongly dependent on the previous steps. Correlation of data management needs and software functions	9. Provide webinars with hands-on session to train software functions 10. Motivate implementation by defining and communicating the output of a successful onboarding: use case implementation
Implementation	Strongly dependent of Masterdata and system customization	11. Define a workflow to support the publication of data models and use cases developed during and after onboarding 12. Plan resources for post-onboarding implementation support

Table 2. Challenges and Approaches of Establishing RDM services: Guidance, training and support are the foundation for setting up an RDM service once the infrastructure is established. Challenges and approaches are listed for four strategic steps towards implementation thus establishment of a RDM service.

The second version of the training and support concept contains five modules to train researchers to become Domain Data Stewards (DDS) with the aim to develop the BAM Data Store in an institutional RDM system. The modules are listed to give an overview of the objectives and changes of the concept compared to the first version described in 2023²⁴.

1. *Communication module*: Remains as initially defined. It aims to identify the RDM needs of each individual research group and to keep

stakeholders informed throughout the process.

2. *Data model module*: It is new. It aims to train DDS with any background knowledge to digitally represent research processes by mapping them in the openBIS-system. In addition to support DDS in coordinating this work with their colleagues.
3. *Masterdata module*: Contents have been divided into *Masterdata* and *Data model* -modules. The Masterdata module aims to train researchers with any background knowledge of metadata concepts,

24 Ariza de Schellenberger, A. et al. BAM Data Store - An Institutional Approach to Research Data Management (RDM) for Materials Science and

Engineering (MSE). 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10046635>.

with a focus on the definition of openBIS Masterdata.

4. *Implementation module*: It was previously called “hands-on module”. The module aims to train in hands-on sessions specific openBIS-software functions required to enable DDS to customize Inventory and ELN for the group.
5. *Community-building module*: The aims have been newly defined. The module aims to make visible the implementation of the RDM system by the researchers during and after onboarding.

Data Stewardship and RDM tool adoption

Acceptance of tools depends largely on how relevant the tool is to the users, whether it can fulfil the users' expectations, how user-friendly the tool is, and how well users are guided, trained, and supported. Data stewards face challenges related to these aspects, which should be carefully considered when making decisions about RDM tools, when establishing on communication strategies with institutional leadership and users, and when developing guidance, training, and support programs.

After a year of onboarding BAM users into the central RDM system, several challenges have been identified that hinder tool adoption and implementation. Supporting data management during data processing and analysis requires digital representation of the collected data and lies at the interface between agnostic and discipline-specific data management, as it depends on how the researchers analyse data and what skills they have. Therefore, we currently prioritize challenges and approaches identified for “Guidance, training and support” with a focus on RDM needs during data collection and preservation which can be addressed with

the RDM system. Additional resources need to be planned to support post-onboarding implementation of the RDM system, as well as to support RDM during data processing and analysis.

To develop an RDM service, adoption and implementation of the RDM system is crucial. This requires guidance, training and support, which can be developed on the basis of a coherent institutional RDM strategy.

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SEED – The Research Data Management Knowledge Platform at the Julius Kühn Institute

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Expectations for managing, providing, and archiving publicly funded research data and data collected by public institutions are increasing due to both scientific and legal obligations. Technical demands based on ever-growing data volumes and more computationally intensive analyses challenge data stewards daily, making effective and sustainable research data management (RDM) increasingly important.

Background

The Julius Kuehn Institute (JKI) is the Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants in Germany and an independent higher federal authority within the portfolio of the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL). Its tasks are defined by law, and the JKI is divided into three thematic areas: plant genetic diversity and breeding research, protection of cultivated plants and plant health, and agroecosystems. The JKI operates across eighteen specialized institutes at nine locations in Germany, with almost 500 scientists and a corresponding research infrastructure complemented by service units such as library, data processing, and administration. This diversity and fragmentation pose significant challenges, particularly for a relatively small data steward team. Furthermore, the JKI's diverse research topics lead to a wide variety of data types, from genetic data to geodata, resulting in varied RDM

requirements. With hundreds of knowledge portals, databases, web services and data management software solutions, as well as numerous research infrastructures, the JKI has a diverse array of tools for generating, managing, and providing research data. However, many of these infrastructures have developed decentrally and redundantly over the years. Various sources of information about these infrastructures, such as the intranet and other tools, often provide incomplete, scattered, or uncoordinated information. Relevant information frequently reaches researchers through "hearsay" rather than structured dissemination.

The SEED Platform

To address these challenges, our data steward team is developing an interactive information platform on RDM-related topics at the JKI. This platform, named SEED, serves as a first point of contact and first-level support for JKI researchers on RDM. It includes technical and content-related

descriptions of data infrastructures, (teaching) materials, best-practice examples, checklists, templates, and links, as well as experts and contact persons. Researchers can find out about existing data infrastructures in advance of a research project and find suitable information on the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) handling of their research data [1]. A significant advantage of the platform SEED is the enhanced and versatile search and exploration options, such as search bars, graphs, and facets/groups, providing a comprehensive overview and easy navigation. Further aims of SEED is to compile, provide and analyze the data infrastructure inventory catalog to identify duplications, synergies, and obsolete infrastructures. By visualizing RDM-related processes along the data life cycle across the diverse data ecosystem at the JKI, the SEED platform helps identify gaps, develop needs-based improvements, and better orchestrate collaboration among various stakeholders and departments. This includes the data processing department, research coordination, legal department, data protection officers, and data and analysis experts. Clearly defined processes and contact persons (RDM roadmaps) along the data life cycle facilitate daily research routines and data management at the JKI. Additionally, an evaluation of data infrastructures along the FAIR criteria will be conducted within SEED to develop conceptual and technical solutions for making the data more FAIR (FAIR assessment is based on the FAIR Data Self Assessment Tool developed by the ARDC [2]). The catalog also supports queries (e.g., for reporting requirements

on existing databases) and content harvesting in other JKI management tools and perspective allows the integration with other portals (e.g., GovData [3], OpenAgrar [4]) and catalogs of other

research institutions affiliated with BMEL in Germany.

Platform Structure and Functionality

The SEED platform is built on a customized CKAN catalog [5] containing structured information on various entities, such as data infrastructures, materials, and experts. Individual but overlapping schemata for different information entities allow specific and comprehensive tagging. Explorative tools, such as a visual knowledge graph, make the catalog interactively and content-wise explorable.

Besides content-related relationships, the catalog also visualizes actual technical links between data infrastructures, providing valuable information for researchers and technical infrastructure teams from an IT perspective.

Conclusion and Future Directions

Research Data Management knowledge is like a SEED; when shared, it grows and eventually bears fruit for a more FAIR future. The SEED platform at the JKI embodies this philosophy, providing a comprehensive, interactive, and integrated approach to managing the institute's diverse and extensive research data (infrastructure). By fostering collaboration, improving data accessibility and usability, and promoting best practices, SEED

supports the JKI's mission to advance research in cultivated plants and contribute to sustainable agriculture. Looking forward, the SEED platform aims to continually evolve, incorporating feedback from users and advancements in RDM technologies and practices. Future developments may include enhanced data visualization tools, more robust integration with external systems, and expanded training and support resources for researchers. By staying at the forefront of RDM innovation, SEED will continue to support the JKI in meeting its scientific and legal obligations while advancing the frontiers of agricultural research.

In conclusion, SEED is not just a platform but a dynamic and growing ecosystem that nurtures research data management excellence at the JKI, ensuring that data is handled responsibly, efficiently, and in a

way that maximizes its potential to benefit science and society.

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Coscine and Data Stewardship

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Coscine is the research data management platform for research projects, which is developed by the RWTH Aachen's IT Center. It aims to assist researchers in making their data FAIR—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Resusable—from file storage, description of those files with metadata, and collaboration with all participating researchers as well as safely archiving data for ten years in line with good scientific practice.

In this session, we will use three flash talks to present on how data stewards support researchers in using Coscine in their day-to-day work. We will start with the basics: setting up custom application profiles that will be used to annotate data with detailed and semantic metadata. Then, we will show how the Python SDK, which employs Coscine's REST-API to not only just upload files, but also to extract and annotate them with metadata in an automated fashion. Lastly, we will outline efforts to connect electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) to Coscine, both as a file storage but also as an archiving solution.

Equipping Researchers with the Power of Metadata

In my role as a data steward, I help researchers set up custom application profiles to annotate data with detailed metadata, ensuring the findability and reproducibility of data according to the

FAIR principles. Subject-specific combinations of metadata, known as metadata schemata, have become established in various disciplines. However, due to the strict rules often associated with these schemas, Coscine has introduced the term metadata profile or application profile. All files within a resource in Coscine should be accompanied by metadata.

In some cases, users can select from existing application profiles, but if none are suitable, that's where I step in. I work with researchers to discuss the necessary metadata fields, striving to use terms from established dictionaries or ontologies. For creating application profiles, we use the AIMS Generator tool, which not only helps create custom profiles easily but also checks them for syntactical correctness. After a researcher submits an application profile, my role is to review it for correctness, ensuring the proper use of ontology terms. Any changes or suggestions regarding the application profile are discussed with the user in GitLab.

Automating Metadata to Coscine

As a data steward part of my work is to create seamless workflows that allow the easy, efficient use of tools such as Coscine to improve the management of research data. As shown by my colleagues, Coscine ensures that data meets the FAIR

principles via the requirement of metadata. The metadata provides context to the data stored in Coscine so that it is reusable to other researchers in the scientific community. However, the number of metadata fields within the application profile, that are necessary to provide that context, can be quite extensive. It is at that point where I begin my work as the data steward. In order for researchers to feel confident in their decision to use Coscine, we must make it more effortless to get started and decrease the time that is needed by the researchers to upload their data and metadata. I will present how the task of providing this metadata can be made simple by using the Coscine SDK and Python to write scripts which extract necessary metadata from research data files and insert that metadata into the application profile, or metadata form in the Coscine resource.

Connecting Platforms: eLabFTW and Coscine

Coscine takes care of (meta)data storage, while electronic lab notebooks assist researchers in digitally documenting their work. One of the prime advantages of an ELN vs. an analog lab journal is the ability

to link items, including the data belonging to an experiment. However, the database structure behind an ELN does not necessarily support (a) large amounts of data, (b) well-structured data deposition, or (c) easy archival using an institutional infrastructure solution.

Both the ELN eLabFTW and Coscine offer REST APIs. As reported at the DSgG 2022 [1], these can be used to build automated workflows which link not only the two platforms, but also measurement devices. However, such workflows have proven difficult to maintain and a native solution both on the ELN side as well as Coscine is much desired. Here, we will report on how RDM staff and researchers came together to propose a solution to the developers on both ends. Depending on the current state, we will also report the results of this effort.

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Merging DMP into Research Project Management

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Data Management Planning (DMP) should play a crucial role in promoting data management best practices, data sharing, and reuse. However, the practical implementation of DMPs through templates and questionnaires appears to accommodate the funders' quality assurance processes more than serving as functional tools for researchers and research institutions. This approach often prioritizes compliance over usability, potentially limiting the effectiveness of DMPs in facilitating robust data management practices. Therefore, the need to merge existing concepts into a novel Research Output Management Planning (ROMPi) framework is needed to address these limitations (Della Chiesa & Sikder, 2024). This approach integrates DMP with project management practices, enhancing effectiveness and utility throughout the research lifecycle.

The ROMPi approach is grounded on four main key perspectives. First, it emphasizes a bottom-up, researcher-centric perspective, focusing more on research needs than merely ensuring policy compliance. Second, it broadens the scope of DMPs to encompass all research outputs. Third, it recognizes data stewardship as a strategic project and data stewardship consulting role. Finally, it advocates transitioning from top-down, funder-imposed implementation requirements in terms of questionnaire templates into a model that integrates DMPs with standard project management at the single output/deliverable level.

1) Initial research data management (RDM) and DMP approaches were project-

oriented and researcher-driven, integrating data management within overall project objectives and researcher daily practice (Smale et al., 2020). This project-researcher-centric approach ensured that all aspects of the research process were linked, promoting seamless data management throughout the project lifecycle. The current DMP landscape is policy-driven since there are potentially billions of euros of costs if RDM best practices are not adequately addressed (European Commission, 2018).

2) ROMPi shifts the focus from a narrow data-only perspective to a broader view of any research outputs aligning with the concept of "Research Objects" (Bechhofer et al., 2010). This comprehensive view enhances the FAIRness of all the research outputs and their semantic link and supports open science by recognizing the diverse contributions ultimately aligning with initiatives like the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) and the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information. In the ROMPi approach, data stewards play a crucial role. They are not just passive recipients of DMPs mandated by funders but active participants in project planning. Their involvement ensures the FAIRness of all project outcomes, contributing to effective research data management. ROMPi

advocates for a bottom-up approach, embedding DMPs within the overall research workflow and aligning them with institutional governance structures, thereby

creating a supportive environment for implementing FAIR principles.

3) To foster the advancement of FAIR Data Stewardship, ROMPi calls for a strategic embedding of the data stewards into the institute governance of research projects from proposal writing, planning and execution. The role of the data steward is strategic as an agent of change (Förstner et al., 2023), maximizing the FAIRnes of the project outcomes and aligning with the overall institutional strategies.

4) ROMPi proposes treating RDM and DMP as fundamental aspects of research project management (Huemann & Turner, 2024) rather than a policy compliance standalone process. This integration starts at the work package (WP) level and goes down to the smallest standalone deliverable/research output. It links it with its RDM lifecycle, ensuring continuous adherence to RDM best practices but not exclusively.

ROMPi's practical implementation starts with restructuring the data management section within research proposals. Instead of focusing solely on textual descriptions of data management strategies as required by various funder templates, researchers are encouraged to exploit the work program of the project proposal, highlighting the work packages and research outputs. WP and research outputs are roughly listed and linked to the respective envisaged data management strategies. By adopting this approach, researchers provide the project proposal reviewer with a clear and comprehensive understanding of the most relevant research output management actions and interdependencies for effective reuse, sharing, and preservation. Transitioning from proposal to project execution involves extending the data management section from a project proposal, starting from the already articulated breakdown of WPs and research outputs. During the planning phase, each WP is thoroughly elaborated in

detail, assessing not only the RDM best practices and FAIR requirements but also project management aspects such as human resource availability, infrastructure requirements, competencies training, risk and stakeholder analysis, and scientific communication, to mention a few. The alignment between the proposal phase and project execution ensures that researchers can clearly understand the link between WP management, planned research outputs, RDM actions, and FAIR output publication.

In conclusion, the ROMPi approach represents a transformative shift in DMP practice, advocating for a project-researcher-centric, holistic strategy. ROMPi fundamentally merges DMP into project management, enhancing the utility and effectiveness of RDM, and supporting comprehensive research output management. Finally, the ROMPi approach addresses the shortcomings of traditional DMPs by offering a holistic strategy that integrates seamlessly with project management practices, tackles governance challenges, and supports the overarching objectives of open science.

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LiaScript as a Medium for Creating and Sharing RDM Content

https://liascript.github.io/course/?https://api.allorigins.win/raw?url=https://git.rwth-aachen.de/dl/workshops/creating-a-workshop-with-liascript/-/raw/main/lia/dsgg/workshop_2024_09_11.md#1

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In this presentation, we will discuss the LiaScript markdown dialect and interpreter as a use case for delivering open-source guided and self-paced resources for teaching Research Data Management concepts as a part of the DKZ.2R center for data literacy. DKZ.2R is a consortium of eleven research institutions and research centers, and one of eleven local and national data literacy centers funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the European Union.

We will cover the origin and mechanics of LiaScript, a markdown dialect and interpreter used to develop and deploy open-source, interactive content. LiaScript is parsed and rendered client-side, meaning that a URL is all that is required for someone to view and interact with created content.

We will demonstrate how to create and share content, as well as how to work with others to build and edit existing projects using collaborative tools such as GitHub and GitLab. We will also cover the potential advantages of LiaScript's implementation, including enhancing engagement and accessibility with its specially tailored markdown to build quizzes, reactive content, and provide automated translations and audio accompaniment.

Finally, drawing on our experience creating and presenting workshops as a function of the DKZ.2R project, we will provide a few practical examples of content we have created, ways in which we have explored extending LiaScript to facilitate our needs and requirements, and some of the advantages and pitfalls we have uncovered as a result.

The CREATIVE project - customising a generic repository for domain scientists and creating a data steward network

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The CREATIVE project aims to make the generic repository RADAR4KIT easily accessible and attractive for the domain-specific communities organized in the Climate and Environment Centre (CEC) at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). This aim will be achieved with the help of customized templates and input masks for subject-specific metadata, which enhance the RADAR4KIT usability for the CEC scientists and thus facilitate data publication beyond the generic functionalities of the repository.

At the same time, the subject-specific metadata schemas are harmonised with the schemas used by the NFDI4Earth, the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) for Earth System Sciences (ESS), and the virtual research environment V-FOR-WaTer, which is being developed at KIT in a collaboration between, mainly, hydrologists and computer scientists. This harmonisation effort in combination with corresponding interfaces enable the domain-specific (meta) data to be included in the data base of NFDI4Earth and promotes broader use of the data beyond KIT. Additionally, by implementing the interfaces and the standardized metadata description, the CEC researchers can use V-FOR-WaTer to pre-process, edit and

visualize the data, thus accelerating scientific work with the data sets and their interdisciplinary use. RADAR4KIT then functions as an adapted specialist repository for the CEC institutes and connects meaningfully to other initiatives. The adaptation steps for the templates can be transferred to other specialist areas at KIT and via detailed documentation and publication with NFDI4Earth also in other domains in the ESS.

Another key focus of the CREATIVE project is connecting and supporting the data stewards at the CEC institutes. For the most part there are no designated positions for this task, so usually researchers and PhD students take on the role unofficially and out of necessity - often without a clear overview of existing research data management (RDM) structures, tools and support. CREATIVE aims to facilitate the exchange between data stewards using the example of publishing data via RADAR4KIT, supported by the CREATIVE team. Several workshops during the development of the metadata templates and during the testing phase are meant to further strengthen this exchange and establish a network of data stewards, thus, supporting sustainable and future-proof research data management (RDM) at KIT.

Fig. 1: Overview of the relations between the CREATIVE project and other structures and initiatives at KIT and beyond. ZKU: climate and environment centre at KIT, RADAR4KIT: institutional repository

The Skills4EOSC Training Curriculum for Data Stewards

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Introduction

Skills4EOSC ‘Skills for the European Open Science commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science’ is a large European project that aims to advance Open Science skills by unifying the current training landscape in Europe. The aim is to close three current gaps: the lack of Open Science and data expertise, the lack of a clear definition of data professional profiles and corresponding career paths, and the fragmentation of training resources. This poster presents the state-of-the-art of a training curriculum for entry-level data stewards developed by Skills4EOSC (Task 4.1) and offers collaboration for piloting parts of the curriculum.

Background

Data stewardship is on the rise across Europe, including Germany. Data stewards are often at the forefront of putting Open Science principles into practice. They work with stakeholders within universities to establish, govern and maintain processes to collect research data, make it usable for research objectives, facilitate its transformation into research outputs, assist in quality assurance, and support informed decision-making on its openness for reuse according to ethical, legal and social expectations. Although the need for good data stewardship is increasingly recognized, comprehensive training programs for data stewards are still lacking across Europe.

Curriculum development

Skills4EOSC is therefore developing a curriculum for data stewards that covers the basic skills and required background knowledge, and is broad enough to be adapted for use in all European countries. As part of a FAIR-by-design approach that reuses existing materials to the greatest extent possible, the curriculum builds on an existing course, ‘Essentials for Data Support’, which is hosted and delivered by the RDNL (Research Data Netherlands) and covers various topics relevant to data stewardship. In addition, we have scoped out other training materials aimed at data stewards and are incorporating these as much as possible. The curriculum currently has the following major sections:

1. Foundation
2. Research Data Management
3. Research Software Management
4. Policy and Governance
5. Usage Rights and Licences
6. Ethics
7. Personal Data and GDPR
8. Teaching and Education
9. Management and Soft skills

Each section is broken down into modules that cover specific topics. For example, in section 2 (Research Data Management), participants will delve into key principles, strategies, and technical aspects crucial for effective data management, including modules covering topics such as metadata, data curation, and data management plans. For each module, the curriculum provides learning objectives, key messages,

suggested resources (in English), and instructor notes. These aspects have been collaboratively developed by international groups of RDM experts from the Skills4EOSC project. At this point, the groups have elaborated the aforementioned aspects for most modules in the curriculum and are now in the process of further refining the modules as to specific details.

Piloting the curriculum

The next step involves piloting parts of the curriculum and gathering feedback to facilitate further enhancements. We are therefore currently looking for potential partners who are willing to pilot any part of

this curriculum at their institute. This could involve teaching individual modules or entire sections depending on the needs and resources at the partner's institute. We will support our partners during their pilot and gather feedback on the curriculum's usefulness in the envisioned final format.

Overall, we hope that, upon completion, the curriculum will become a major resource for developing training programs for data stewards in Europe, thereby contributing to the establishment of good data stewardship at European universities and other institutions.

Enhancing Research Data Management: A Chemistry-Specific Exercise Catalogue

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Workshops for researchers or students on research data management (RDM) skills are often offered by central RDM service facilities at universities or non-university research institutions. Although the basic aspects of RDM are discussed, there are often no discipline-specific examples or tools, so participants often lack a tangible relevance to their own research activities and would like to see more practical examples from their own daily laboratory work.

NFDI4Chem, the chemistry consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure, has been offering RDM training courses since 2021, teaching the basics of RDM in a chemistry context. Through a series of practical exercises, both face-to-face and online, participants create entry points into RDM and develop practical procedures for generating FAIR research data.

In order to enable the reusability of the workshop, NFDI4Chem is currently developing a catalogue of exercises²⁵ that will provide both disciplinary and non-disciplinary RDM staff with specific examples and suggestions for designing an RDM workshop with a high degree of practical relevance to chemistry. The catalogue will categorise exercises by RDM

topic and exercise type. Information on the duration of the exercise, a detailed description of the exercise with equipment requirements, recommendations for embedding in the overall context and examples enable direct implementation in RDM training courses or curricular teaching. The exercises included have been tested and developed within NFDI4Chem by its RDM trainers or have been inspired by previously published RDM training materials.

The exercises use portals such as the PubChem database, the re3data registry, the Chemotion and RADAR4Chem repositories, the NFDI terminology service and the open access Beilstein Journal of Organic Chemistry. In addition, the importance of metadata can be explored using reaction schemes, NMR spectra or microscopy images. A catalogue of requirements for the use of electronic laboratory books or a data management plan based on a chemical project description can be developed. Suggestions for generic exercises with chemistry-specific recommendations, e.g. on data lifecycle, FAIR principles, process management, data storage or repetition of previously taught aspects of RDM complete the exercise catalogue.

²⁵ Hausen, D. A., Schröter, A., Andres, A.-C., & Golub-Overbeck, B. (2024, August 21). 27 FAIR

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Community Data Stewardship Training with the Digital Research Academy

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Caring about data and its quality, ensuring correct and ethical data handling and other data stewardship tasks are vital for quality research. Many researchers, however, never learn how to practise data stewardship. At the same time the data steward profession is becoming increasingly important to run complex data-related projects and as has been estimated already in 2020, we will need 500,000 data stewards for European research alone (<https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00505-7>).

There is a clear gap between the required knowledge and the needed skill set. How do we teach data stewardship skills to researchers and how do we train the next generation of data stewards – a profession that is a second career path for many? We need many pieces to solve this puzzle: data stewardship master programs, data stewardship training for researchers and research staff, data stewardship certificate programs, consulting and support, short form training, long form training, and more.

The [Digital Research Academy](#) (DRA) is a trainer network with the goal of improving the quality of research and we believe that data stewardship is a core competency needed for research quality. We want to be a valuable puzzle piece in providing data stewardship training for research organisations and people working in research. The DRA works closely with academic research institutions to tailor interactive training experiences to meet their specific needs. By collaborating with these institutions, we ensure that our training materials and methods are aligned with the latest practices and address the unique challenges faced by each organisation.

All of our expert trainers undergo our Train-the-Trainer program, which emphasises pedagogy, didactics, and community knowledge sharing. This program equips them with the skills and practical experience needed to effectively educate others. Additionally, this program is available to academic institutions as a tailored training, enabling them to create multipliers for data stewardship within their own organisations. We believe that we need people who care about research quality to be involved in training data stewardship and in this poster we want to share our concept of providing bespoke training by expert trainers that empathise with the learners and help them get from where they are now to data stewardship heroes.

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Data Steward's Workflow in NFDI-MatWerk

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Data stewards undergo professionalization within a project, primarily tailored to its specific needs. Their expertise, competence, and accumulated knowledge have spurred a bottom-up approach, delineating effective support within the MSE community. This perspective doesn't diminish the significance of other intermediary roles of data stewards; rather, it underscores how this sequential task approach is especially adept in this context.

This Poster illustrates that consistent support starts early in the Material Science Engineering (MSE) requirements identification process, working closely with scientists to develop Infrastructure Use Cases (IUCs). This support continues through the development phase and reaches its peak during service delivery, ensuring the successful implementation and optimization of the developed solutions for practical applications.

Data Steward Service Center – the FAIRagro RDM-expertise hub

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FAIRagro [1] is the NFDI consortium for the agrosystem sciences (focusing mainly on plant, soil and environment research). As a central institution within FAIRagro, the Data Steward Service Center (DSSC) aims to harmonize data management and is one of the most important connecting points between FAIRagro and the scientific agrosystem community and beyond. The DSSC organizes the continuous exchange of research data management (RDM) knowledge and experience. It consists of the FAIRagro data stewards, who are experts in the field of RDM for agrosystem research. They channel user requests and feedback from the community to FAIRagro developers. Knowledge about products and services is collected from the developers, translated and passed along to the community as part of professional trainings. The well-trained data stewards bring together expertise on data from different parts of the agrosystem science like soil data, general field data, genetic data

(„omics data“), phenotyping data, field robotics & sensor data, and big geo data [2]. These competencies are embedded in the context of FAIRagro’s research disciplines, ranging cross-scale from genes, phenomics, crop trials and management to landscapes and regions. They include different data categories comprising sensitive data, time series, remote sensing, omics and geo data. Further, the DSSC offers legal support, looking at questions dealing with e.g. anonymisation/pseudonymisation or copyright and licenses. Knowledge and expertise is pooled to provide the full range of expertise to the community. This understanding of these different FAIRagro disciplines and the integrative work of the data stewards will foster the coalescence of the community.

The DSSC provides the following services: The FAIRagro data stewards, working together as the DSSC, form the FAIRagro

Helpdesk. There, they act as interface between the agricultural community and the developers of the FAIRagro products. They have a comprehensive understanding of data issues, process support requests from the helpdesk (2nd level support) and establish contact to the developers if necessary (3rd level support). Besides the personal support for the community, easy-to-understand materials, like a list of repository recommendations [3] or a collection of Open Educational Resources (OER) [4], are collected in the FAIRagro Toolbox where they provide low-threshold access to FAIRagro-relevant information (1st level support).

Next to the hands-on support on specific questions via the helpdesk, trainings tailored to the needs of the users of the FAIRagro infrastructure and data management requests are offered. This includes cooperations with other RDM service providers like other NFDI consortia, universities, universities of applied sciences and non university research institutions. These trainings are prepared and organized by the closely related training and education unit of FAIRagro and conducted in close cooperation with the data stewards. In addition to general training and specific RDM courses, reusable training materials in the sense of Open Educational Resources (OER) are created. As a central document, a training manual will be written jointly by the training coordinators and data stewards to enable trainers to design their own training courses on RDM in agrosystem research.

With our poster we explain how the DSSC is integrated into the agrosystem community, what the expertise of our data stewards are, what services they support and how they can be contacted in terms of RDM questions. Further, we inform about our close connections between the data stewards and the FAIRagro training unit.

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Research data management and data stewardship as a multilevel model: challenges and solutions

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The demand for high-quality work with research data is rising with the creation of multi-center, nationwide research and health infrastructures like the German Centre for Mental Health (DZPG) (Halil et al., 2024). Data stewards play a crucial role in this context. However, a strong heterogeneity in the respective areas of application and the subject-specific prior knowledge of data stewards increase difficulties in the effective handling of research data. There is a lack of a precise definition of the role and tasks of data stewardship (cf. Jetten et al., 2021). The diversity of job descriptions makes it difficult to communicate tasks to newcomers in a targeted manner. Therefore, sustainable strategies for research data management (RDM) depend on adequate framework conditions, which require both institutional and inter-institutional support and measures.

Within the DZPG and Konsort/SWD projects, training opportunities for RDM staff (e.g., data stewards) have been developed, which promote professionalisation in RDM through certificate courses and self-learning units (Liu et al., 2024). The Research Data and Results Centre (RDRC) shall provide the DZPG with a FAIR archiving and publication infrastructure for psychosocial data from evidence-based research (Halil et al., 2024). In addition, an exchange format for data stewards has been created in which problem- and goal-oriented

discussions are held. In a broader sense, the exchange of data stewards still seems complicated, networks are often difficult to reach or poorly organised, depending on the field of application. Better networking of data stewards within and across institutions must be realised.

We view RDM as a reciprocal, multi-level model, within strategic (European and national), institutional, and individual levels. This allows the challenges and opportunities of sustainable RDM to be mapped and their reciprocity to be emphasised. It leads us to the following points: The role of the data steward as a mediator in scientific exchange must be strengthened in the long term. As there are numerous publications on RDM and data stewardship, these must be evaluated in order to drive forward the further development and improvement of existing products and services. Finally, working groups should be seen as 'incubators' for successful research data management. The exchange of experience and flow of information between NFDI, state initiatives (strategic level) and institutions (operational level) should be more straightforward in order to initiate the best possible developments in the field of RDM (Herres-Pawlis et al., 2022). German and national RDM strategies could benefit from the experience of their European neighbours like the Netherlands, as they already have established comprehensive multi-level RDM strategies on a national

level (cf. Jetten et al., 2021). What is needed is a coordinated and united (local, regional, and national) approach to formalise and professionalise the role of data stewardship in Germany.

Setting an example of advanced stewardship practices at a national level should have a signalling effect on the levels below. It seems necessary to combine effective "top down" and "bottom up" strategies in order to enable long-term change in the context of data stewardship developments in Germany.

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Addressing Research Data Management Challenges Through Networks – an Approach for Community-Driven Collaboration

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Research data management (RDM) poses unique challenges influenced by domain-specific factors and organizational contexts. While some challenges demand tailored, domain-specific solutions, can others, such as ethical considerations and data visibility, are ubiquitous across research domains.

With this poster contribution we will present GO UNITE!²⁶, a community-driven approach for addressing challenges in RDM. We will advocate for a national RDM community network for working collaboratively on common RDM hurdles.

The community-driven RDM network

GO UNITE!, the German chapter of the GO FAIR Data Stewardship Competence Centers (DSCC-IN)²⁷, was founded in 2020 and is community-driven in the sense that it is organized non-hierarchically and no official membership or institutional belonging is needed to be part of it. Everybody is invited to participate for as long as they wish. Participants of the network collaborate on RDM challenges that were identified by temporary working groups. Participants of the network can suggest RDM topics and challenges to address collaboratively, based on what is

relevant to their daily work. If a sufficient number of participants agree on a suggested RDM topic, a temporary self-organized working group is founded. Due to this level of community-driven organization, the participants of GO UNITE! only focus on aspects that they encounter in their daily activities, in order not to increase the work load of each participant. When a group reaches its self-defined achievements, the group disbands or rests until there is a need for further exchange.

In two general meetings every year, the working groups present and discuss their final or intermediate results with the participants of GO UNITE! and the wider RDM community. In addition, an international RDM topic is presented in each workshop in order to look beyond the national RDM horizon.

Since the establishment of GO UNITE! in 2020, five temporary working groups were founded:

- *Research data management training* – defining concepts of RDM training and collecting RDM training materials
- *Modeling research data management* – working on the formal description of RDM, the

²⁶ <https://go-unite.de>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

²⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/dscc/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

organization and documentation of RDM counseling services²⁸

- *Ethics in research data management* – dealing with ethical aspects regarding RDM²⁹
- *Collection and visibility of research data* – establishing concepts for raising the visibility of published research data for institutions e.g., universities³⁰
- *Accessibility of research data* – working on concepts for raising the accessibility of research data and more awareness for the topic³¹

Four of these temporary working groups are ongoing. Due to the fact that challenges in RDM training are also addressed by many other networks, such as the working group “Schulung/Fortbildungen”³² in the *Deutsche Initiative für Netzwerkinformation e.V.*³³, the activities of the working group *research data management training* were implemented in these other networks too.

Challenges and Potentials of the RDM network

The organizational approach of GO UNITE! allows us to address only RDM challenges with which a crucial mass of participants have to deal with. However, the non-hierarchical structure and the missing institutional anchoring (as well as the absence of any funding) can lead to a less

constant participation of the members of the working groups. Due to the fact, that there is no institutional obligation in the participation and considering the many tasks we have to tend to in our jobs, the network cannot always count on stable and intense commitment on the part of its participants.

However, by addressing only RDM challenges that are defined by the participants themselves and relying on flat hierarchies, we can make sure that everybody can draw benefits from the work in the network.

Results of the RDM network

Since 2020 the working groups of the RDM network have achieved different goals. Besides participations at different RDM related workshops und conferences³⁴, they took part in the process of commenting the planned research data law in Germany,³⁵ organized several workshops with the wider RDM community³⁶ and published recommendations with the double goal of organizing RDM counselling services (Helling, Lemaire and Kellendonk 2022) and improving the visibility of research data for institutions (Putnings et al. 2024).

28 <https://go-unite.de/index.php/ag-fdm-beschreibungsmodell/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

29 <https://go-unite.de/index.php/ag-forschungsethik/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

30 <https://go-unite.de/index.php/ag-sammlung-und-sichtbarkeit/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024)

31 <https://go-unite.de/index.php/ag-inklusion-im-forschungsdatenmanagement/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

32 https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/UAG_Schulungen/Fortbildungen/, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

33 <https://dini.de/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

34 e.g. [https://www.uni-hildesheim.de/veranstaltungen/artikel/online-coffee-](https://www.uni-hildesheim.de/veranstaltungen/artikel/online-coffee-lectures-go-fair-go-unite/)

<https://events.tib.eu/vbib22/vbib22-programm/programmdetail/vbib22-wandel-corner-3-2/>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8395229>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

35 https://www.bmbf.de/bmbf/shareddocs/faq/240305_forschungsdatengesetz.html (last access: 15th of May 2024).

36 e.g. <https://go-unite.de/index.php/events-workshop-ag-fdm-beschreibungsmodell-17-05-2023/>; <https://go-unite.de/index.php/events-workshop-ag-fdm-beschreibungsmodell-12-05-2022/>; <https://go-unite.de/index.php/events-workshop-ag-fdm-beschreibungsmodell-05-05-2022/>; <https://go-unite.de/index.php/events-workshop-ag-fdm-beschreibungsmodell-07-07-2021/>, (last access: 2nd of July 2024).

Our poster presentation

We are convinced that the organization of temporary working groups within a RDM network through the definition, by its participants themselves, of RDM challenges is an effective way to ensure that collaborative work is both problem- and goal-oriented without increasing the workload on the individual. In our poster we will present the organizational structures of GO UNITE! more in detail. In addition, we will focus on the different working groups and their achievements so as to illustrate the productive output of networks like the one described.

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Integration of data management approaches in pre-clinical laboratory workflows

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Most attempts in the neuroscience community to organise data and analyse it in a standardised way focus on complex multi-dimensional data as in *in-vivo* recordings and human MRI data sets. Only recently have first attempts started to standardise “simpler” data sets such as electrophysiological recordings *in-vitro*, as they are often found in pre-clinical studies. Unfortunately, these tools are often not easily approachable for scientists without a coding background and can appear intimidating or require proprietary software, potentially leading to divergences from recommended standards. Differences between laboratories and the protocols used make it further challenging to find common ground for data management and analyses. This is especially challenging in fields such as cellular electrophysiology, where over the last decades vast amounts of acquisition hardware and software have been developed, leading to very diverse data strategies.

Following FAIR guidelines is a crucial part of improving reproducibility and transparency in the scientific field. Successful implementation of the guidelines requires research data management (RDM) strategies and an understanding of how RDM can facilitate personal analysis and data sharing capabilities, improving collaboration inside and outside one's own laboratory.

Members of the laboratory took part in surveys and 1-on-1 interviews to assess the requirements of scientists and their project's needs and workflows to find common ground and elicit existing standards. To reduce the barrier of following standards in practice, a tool with a low entry barrier and high benefit was developed with the help of users.

First, existing standards, challenges and analytical needs were discussed. Additionally, the workload resulting from analysis steps and data organisation was assessed using a questionnaire. Interview feedback was used to inform further steps for the development of workflows. Agreed standards included methods of documenting experiments and analysis, metadata, and tools to work on the data. Increased accessibility and reusability by implementing workflows made use of established open-source data types such as Neurodata without borders (NWB). Convergence on a single data format simplifies the exchange of data within the laboratory and follows requirements set by data repositories. Given the previously agreed upon standards for metadata collection and structures, guidance was provided on how to convert measurement data to NWB. This guidance was partially provided by a Python based laboratory community open-source tool with conversion, metadata input, and analysis functionality which integrates already existing data pipelines and makes them available to others. Scientists actively contributed to the development of functionality by being either directly involved in the coding or by providing crucial feedback. As further support, standards and workflows are communicated to new members of the laboratory as part of “data

onboarding”, facilitating access to analysis pipelines and documentation practices and fossilising established standards.

In conclusion, integration of different RDM concepts into standardised workflows for specialised electrophysiological data structures lets scientists actively participate in the development of procedures with the aim to reduce workload, enable more transparency and lower the burden of data sharing, crucial for improving reproducibility.

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BEXIS2 – a user-friendly Platform for Metadata Management

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BEXIS2 is a free and open-source community-driven web-based research data management system [1,2]. It is an extensible and customisable system that allows for the development of new functions and modification of its various components from database schemes to the user interface [3]. It helps researchers keep track of their data, eases data sharing for collaborative projects, and alleviates the effort of data management for multicentral/longitude studies. Besides the web interface, it provides access to content for 3rd party software and services via API calls.

Initially designed for biodiversity data, BEXIS2 can be adopted to other fields. For instance, in the Cluster of Excellence ‘Balance of the Microverse’ [4] we are instantiating it as a meta-data management platform, which facilitates the integration of different types of data generated in microbiological experiments or collected in the natural environment. In this contribution, we will provide technical details on the BEXIS2 platform, and

discuss our meta-data management workflows.

The work is supported by the grant provided by Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation), Projekt ‘EXC 2051: Balance of the Microverse’, No 390713860.

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Establishing Sustainable and Functional Research Data Management (RDM) in Neuroscience: The RETAIN Fellowship Program

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Establishing sustainable and functional research data management (RDM) in heterogeneous and collaborative research environments, such as a Cluster of Excellence, remains challenging. Despite promising FDM initiatives like NFDI consortia, achieving the goal of producing reusable, well-annotated, FAIR-compliant data remains particularly difficult in a neuroscience research setting. General RDM practices, including the use of DMP templates, general-purpose data repositories, and naming conventions, often fall short in overcoming the significant structural hurdles inherent to diverse research methodologies, paired with varying devices, technique combinations, or complex data properties. The lack of resources and time often prevents researchers from overcoming these obstacles, which, while specific to their environment, likely exist elsewhere as well. While employing external expertise, such as programmers, can be initially helpful, it may create unsustainable dependencies.

The best expertise and understanding of data generation and processing come from within the research team itself. Therefore, the solution to overcoming RDM obstacles and developing best practices must be created by data producers within the research environment, considering the team's needs and capabilities.

As part of NeuroCure's Cluster of Excellence initiative to promote FAIR data sharing, the Research Data Management

Implementation in the Neurosciences (RETAIN) Fellowships were established. Each fellowship is a 50% FTE position for 24 months, targeting researchers with a PhD or near completion, who demonstrate a keen interest in RDM, high data literacy, and openness to further education. Applicants must submit a working plan outlining the current RDM status, existing obstacles, and desired goals for a successful and functional RDM environment. Fellows collaborate with NeuroCure's Coordinator for Value and Open Science through regular online meetings, guidance, and progress tracking using OpenProject. Additionally, fellows receive online training on RDM fundamentals. Fellows also report their progress to the governing board of the NeuroCure cluster. For the first call, two fellowships were provided to applicants from a preclinical and clinical neuroscience research setting.

A key aspect of the RETAIN program is the integration and acceptance of developed solutions by the research team. Fellows are required to develop workflows, educational materials, onboarding processes, and templates tailored to their team's needs. Successful completion of the RETAIN fellowship will result in a research environment with a sustainable RDM system, serving as a model for other laboratories using similar techniques and data, both within and outside the NeuroCure cluster. Fellows will gain

theoretical and practical RDM skills and problem-solving experience, making them competitive for data stewardship positions. All materials, code, and software developed during the fellowships will be published openly.

In conclusion, RDM-focused fellowships like RETAIN aim to implement lasting and functional local RDM structures. They

generate new tools, workflows, and templates, and produce data stewards who are experienced researchers with deep understanding of data literacy, standardization, and specialized data management. Such experts and model laboratories are essential to realizing a FAIR data landscape in the neurosciences and beyond.

TUM Research Data Hub: A new service structure for generic and project-specific RDM with Data Stewards

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In 2023, the Technical University of Munich (TUM) established the TUM Research Data Hub as a central entity for all institutional research data management (RDM) services. The University Library (UB) operates the hub in cooperation with the cross-faculty Munich Data Science Institute (MDSI) to offer practical, tailored solutions for sustainable RDM. These include not only institutional RDM services but also a pool of Data Stewards responsible for RDM in large-scale projects. To our knowledge, this innovative staffing concept is new and unique in the German university landscape. It creates new personnel resources within the University Library: Data Steward positions approved within the framework of third-party-funded large projects are supplemented by central funds from TUM. Data Stewards hired for these positions are organizationally assigned either to the UB or the MDSI and are integrated into research projects after

training.

In these projects, Data Stewards implement RDM for and with project members while also addressing the general RDM needs of TUM. The organizational affiliation with the Hub promotes the exchange of experiences and results from the projects as well as collegial support in developing project-related or generic RDM solutions. This generates synergy effects, makes insights centrally available to all, and provides resources for university-wide RDM support coordinated by the Hub beyond project-specific requirements. The poster depicts the structure of the TUM Research Data Hub and its integration within the Technical University of Munich. It describes the staffing concept of the Data Stewards located within the Hub, the service portfolio, and initial experiences with this new service structure.

Agents of Change – Skills & Strategies for Data Stewards and RDM professionals. A Workshop Concept.

DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/14070665>

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The role of Research Data Management (RDM) professionals, including Data Stewards, Research Data Managers, and Data Curators, is increasingly critical in the scientific community at both national and international levels. Job advertisements for these positions vary widely, encompassing general RDM support, discipline-specific roles, project-based assignments, and positions within libraries, computer centers, and other institutions or service units. To meet the growing demand for skilled professionals, numerous training programs and courses have emerged, catering to career changers and those pursuing degrees in RDM. Initiatives such as Train-the-Trainer and various technical courses provide valuable education, covering basic and advanced RDM knowledge. However, they often lack training on fostering a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data culture and developing relevant strategies. Job advertisements for RDM professionals can be vague or differ from actual work practices. New RDM services, in particular, may suffer from a lack of clear role definitions and an understanding of the impact RDM professionals have within their institutions or projects. Addressing this gap, a new training initiative integrated into the KonsortSWD work program aims to support RDM professionals as change agents who significantly contribute to implementing FAIR data and Open Science principles. To our knowledge, this training is unique. The need for such a program is supported by feedback from Data Stewards and other RDM professionals and is echoed in current

European initiatives like the Minimal Viable Skillset for Data Stewards (Skills4EOSC)[1]. This program explores the roles of RDM professionals, including Data Stewards and Research Data Managers, considering the current state of data stewardship in Germany and abroad.

Participants will learn about and discuss required competencies for their daily work and engage with self-marketing strategies to enhance communication about their work and collaboration with stakeholders. The program delves into essential skills and strategies for professional growth, resilience fundamentals, and stakeholder analysis. This also includes goal setting, understanding the impact of changes on stakeholders, learning about change management, and explore self-efficacy resources. Additionally, the program offers a list of networking opportunities and introduces a participant buddy program to foster connections.

In summary, this training project fills a significant gap in the current landscape of RDM professional development. By focusing on the practical and strategic aspects of data stewardship, it empowers RDM professionals to be effective change agents in their institutions. This workshop aims to provide confidence in their roles to promote FAIR data practices and contribute to the broader goals of Open Science. Through networking and continuous development, participants will be better equipped to navigate the challenges of working in the field of research data management. We invite participants of the

Data Stewardship Goes Germany Workshop to discuss this workshop concept critically and provide valuable feedback on their own experiences. The first iterations of this workshop concept are planned in October and November of 2024.

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Designing and Implementing a Practical Data Management Strategy in RDMO for the DFG SPP2419 HyCAM Priority Program

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The DFG Priority Program SPP 2419 HyCAM (Hydrogen-based fuel Combustion using Additive Manufacturing) employs a highly interdisciplinary approach by facilitating collaboration across various disciplines, encompassing chemistry, combustion science, and additive manufacturing. The main goal is to exploit the design flexibility of additive manufacturing to enable optimized, efficient, and safe hydrogen-based fuel combustion. The Priority Program (PP) comprises 10 projects, each with three to four sub-projects (i.e., experimental combustion, numerical combustion, and additive manufacturing). It involves 82 scientific staff members (i.e., 34 doctoral researchers, 17 post-doctoral researchers, and 31 Principal investigators (PIs)).

Proactive coordination within the Priority Program plays a crucial role in leveraging synergies and achieving its scientific objectives. The Coordination Project of the Priority Program implements Research Data Management (RDM) practices, facilitates the dissemination of research findings, and fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange within DFG SPP2419 HyCAM. Enforcing and monitoring RDM practices in the SPP2419 projects throughout the entire period of this DFG Priority Program is key to successfully attaining HyCAM's objectives. RDM is a

fundamental principle in good scientific practice, outlined by DFG, which aims to generate and manage high-quality, secure, sustainable, and reusable research data in accordance with FAIR principles. The implementation of RDM within the Priority Program is challenged by the extensive variety of data types, making standard research data management templates impractical. A strategic hierarchical structure has been designed and implemented in the Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) [1], based on the parent project option, to streamline the process of planning and documenting data management of each project. Specifically, the DFG SPP2419 HyCAM Coordination project has been assigned as the main parent of the remaining ten projects belonging to this Priority Program. Similarly, each project has been assigned as a parent project for the three to four sub-projects belonging to the same project. This project hierarchy enables a centralized collection of all Data Management Plans (DMPs) prepared by all HyCAM members. It empowers project members to access all DMPs of their co-workers and facilitates collaborations among the sub-projects of the same SPP2419 project. Additionally, a specific SPP2419 Data Management Plan (DMP) template (in the form of a specific customized SPP2419 catalog) has been tailored for the interdisciplinary

collaborations within the HyCAM Priority Program to ensure compliance with the DFG guidelines for safeguarding good research data [2] and the EU Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 [3]. Such a customized catalog has been made available on RDMO. It enables all HyCAM projects to efficiently develop their DMPs by guiding them through a series of well-defined questions, ensuring that their research data is properly documented and managed. The practical data management strategy implemented in RDMO for the DFG SPP2419 HyCAM Priority Program enables the Coordination Project to enhance RDM measures and promote interdisciplinary collaborations within HyCAM. Effective management of the extensive research data produced is essential for generating high-quality,

secure, sustainable, and reusable scientific results in alignment with the FAIR principles.

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Metadata in research data repositories: fulfillment of international standards and individual requirements

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Research data repositories are becoming increasingly established in the portfolio of Collaborative Research Centers (CRCs). The application scenarios for research data repositories are very diverse and characterized by heterogeneous requirements. The aim of research data repositories is to make research data and their metadata searchable and accessible according to the FAIR principles, in order to support its further use in the research cycle in the best possible way. In particular, the selection or development of a suitable metadata schema poses a challenge against the background of heterogeneous data types and the fact that standardization is only just beginning, for example, in the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). In addition, the practice of research data management has shown that the early assignment of meaningful and complete metadata during the research process is key to the implementation of FAIR data.

Both the development of metadata schemas and the indexing of information lie within the core competencies of academia, but are still a young field of activity for research data. This study shows two successful approaches to develop metadata schemas in two research areas,

as well as the design and implementation of organizing structures using these schemas in a research data repository based on the Dataverse software.

In the CRC/TRR 196 MARIE, which focuses on Terahertz research, a specific metadata schema was developed, based on the EngMeta schema, and by implementing the competency questions concept in close cooperation with the researchers of the CRC. This concept allows the actual knowledge holders, who are the researchers, to be involved in the creation process (Apke et al., 2004; Staab, 2002) . The goal is to transform the researchers' tacit knowledge into explicit knowledge. This method lets the participants assume that there is a comprehensive omniscient database with well-developed research data from this domain and asks them to formulate questions that they would like to ask to this database. Competency questions are a set of questions and controlled statements formulated and answered in natural language. They can be used to identify important elements and relationships in a domain while representing functional requirements for a model (Bezerra et al., 2014; Schnurr et al., 2001; Vedurmudi et

al., 2021). The required information to design the metadata schema can then be extracted from the questions. This is done by formalizing the questions in first-order logic, i.e., abstracting the concrete questions into more general statements (Noy & Hafner, 1997). Deriving from this, metadata field considerations can then be made and extracted (Alashloo et al., 2022).

In the CRC/TR 296 Locotact, which focuses on thyroid hormone research, a metadata schema was similarly tailored to the specific requirements of medical research. The steps to the development of the metadata schema for Locotact involved a step-by-step development and revision process during exchange meetings, with input from an expert committee of the CRC/TRR (comprising approximately five project PIs) and metadata experts from the Research Data Services (library of University of Duisburg-Essen). The Locotact metadata schema will be further developed to better align with the evolving needs of researchers.

These two approaches considered both the different starting points regarding existing metadata standards and their development in the NFDI, as well as the individual requirements for internal subject-specific references. The article compares the approaches, highlighting their advantages and disadvantages, and identifies elements of a general approach.

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Come2Data - National Data Competence Center with a focus on Saxony

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A **consortial** project involving the Chemnitz University of Technology, Leipzig University, Saxon State and University Library Dresden (SLUB Dresden), Dresden University of Technology (TU Dresden, coordinating office), funded by the European Union (NextGenerationEU) and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)

Come2Data is one of eleven national data competence centers currently being established in Germany. It pursues a regional approach, focusing on the federal state of Saxony, as well as an interdisciplinary approach to provide practice-oriented data skills. Come2Data's services are primarily directed towards the scientific community, but can also support the administrative sector, the interested public and business communities, in the long run. The aim is to consolidate the diverse local, regional and national activities that exist in Saxony and synergistically combine them into a sustainable source for data literacy development. This will be based on a comprehensive range of training and support services in the areas of data management, data integration, data analysis and data publication. Come2Data bundles existing data science training and support services from the four institutions directly involved in the project implementation of the consortium, as well as collecting expertise and commitment to research data management from a wider network, e.g. in SaxFDM (an initiative of Saxonian research and higher education institutions to cooperate and coordinate activities surrounding research data management), and the National Research

Data Infrastructure (NFDI). Both dimensions are complemented by high-performance computing and analysis methods for data-intensive interdisciplinary research applications, such as artificial intelligence and data modeling provided by the national AI Competence Centers (e.g. via ScADS.AI).

In addition, Come2Data runs four pilot projects which serve both as a source of concrete data expertise and of actual service demands emerging from the (daily) work on data-intensive, real-world example use cases.

The consolidated range of training, support and knowledge will be made available to researchers, teachers and students via a virtual platform with a high public profile. Come2Data will act as a place of learning and support as well as a place for research and networking.

As an open place of learning, Come2Data will consolidate existing courses on data skills, process them didactically for different target groups and make them available centrally as a series of modules and certification programs. This will also integrate findings and solutions from the research laboratories, where complex data and teaching problems will be addressed

by a Saxon data expert pool as part of the aforementioned pilot projects.

A sustainable support center will be created around the research and learning facilities, which will provide extensive level 1 support in the form of a helpdesk using a knowledge base and specific level 2 support through the connection of clients with specialists who have a specific skill set or expertise. As an open networking location, these services will be available to a broad target group. In addition, Come2Data creates a space in which solutions for real data and teaching problems can be provided by tested local, regional and national experts via a free exchange of information, and where these solutions will be presented in a didactic manner.

As an overarching goal Come2Data will contribute to the implementation of a German-wide network of data competence centers, NFDI consortia, RDM service

providers and other initiatives subserving data support. To this end, a common knowledge base is planned, as well as a network-wide crosslinked helpdesk system.

Data stewards could benefit from Come2Data services in various ways. Data stewards would be able to find practical solutions for complex data challenges in the knowledge base and access the expert advice via the helpdesk. The integration of diverse educational content and expertise would provide data stewards an environment of continuous learning and professional development. Through collaboration and networking opportunities provided by Come2Data, data stewards can also exchange best practices and innovative approaches, further enriching their capacity to support data-driven initiatives within their organizations.

The Heliocentric Model of Open Science Documentation: Understanding Data Stewardship Top-Down and Bottom-Up

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Much of Open Science's efforts have focused on outcomes rather than processes, neglecting that what gives science its weight is the rigor of the process by which information was produced and justified, and that hence, exhaustive documentation and scrutiny of those processes, in addition to output data, are the bedrock of a reliable scientific knowledge base. A cursory examination of Open Science infrastructure supports our argument: overwhelming resources go towards archiving output data or supporting Open Access, but very little goes to any of the other facets of Open Science, such as Open Methodology [1]. If the reliability and reproducibility of science depends on accurate records of who did what, when, where, why and how, it becomes imperative to use a paradigm that allows us to easily and systematically keep track of all of this information. We align with past advocacies [2,3,4] on the need to reform knowledge documentation and communication away from the paper-centric publication system by proposing The Heliocentric Model of Open Science Documentation [5] (Helio), a model that encompasses the entirety of the research process.

In this poster, we will describe the theoretical model. Our goal is to use community input to discuss the strengths and weaknesses of the work we have done so as to create a tool that is useful, easy to learn, easy to use, and that can therefore become easily integrated into current workflows so as to ultimately make documenting reliable science as effective as possible.

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DataStew: Peppered and salted

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The poster focuses on a set of five data steward profiles, which has been consolidated after a fruitful/spicy debate with the community.

In early 2023, we presented an analysis/study of the status quo of data stewardship in German academic research institutions. On this basis, we compiled recommendations on how to establish data steward teams to meet different institutional needs [1]. One specific outcome was a set of profiles characterized by a number of dimensions (such as range of tasks/ duties, importance of domain expertise, localization within the institution, and importance of IT skills). We identified five profiles that discriminate between operational, domain and IT focused tasks and consultancy tasks including training. Depending on local requirements, teams of data stewards may be established to effectively support researchers on their data management challenges.

Since the publication of our report, we have received a lot of positive feedback and adoption of the profiles. In two subsequent workshops we collected more detailed feedback on the labelling and perceived importance of each dimension of the profiles, such as IT skills.[2, 3] These have led to a reformulation and adjustment of the dimensions that characterise the profiles.

We provide an updated and consolidated version of the data steward profiles, as they also serve as a fundamental element of

identity in an emerging community of practice. We would also like to use the opportunity of having a significant proportion of the national data steward community present to gather further information on the quantitative needs of specific profiles. This will better inform our recommendations to institutions and projects on how to build effective sustainable data steward teams.

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Data Stewards und Service Stewards - Opportunities for Collaboration

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The German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) and its Base4NFDI initiative have identified the need for a new role called Service Steward, to support the development and integration of NFDI-wide basic services into the national research landscape. Their areas of responsibility are comparable to those of Data Stewards. While they act as an interface between infrastructure and researchers, Service Stewards act as the interface between service development teams and the various NFDI consortia, thus accelerating the development of a cross-disciplinary service portfolio. This similarity suggests possible opportunities for future collaboration, as Data Stewards can benefit from being both relevant stakeholders and multipliers in the context of basic service development.

Since March 2023, the DFG-funded NFDI comprises 26 discipline-specific consortia. In general, these scientific communities operate their own service portfolios, i.e. software tools, technical services or workflows, and offer advice to enable and facilitate researchers to create and work with FAIR data. In the course of that work, cross-cutting and consortia-overlapping topics have emerged which are addressed and discussed in so-called NFDI sections. This is where Base4NFDI comes into play: as a joint initiative of all NFDI consortia, the project promotes cross-disciplinary basic services for a NFDI-wide service portfolio, providing both the development process

and financial framework along with personnel support.

Such a basic service usually builds on already existing service structures, creates added value for all users (compared to individual solutions), and strives for sustainable long-term organisation and provision. As a technical-organisational solution, it may offer new software, processes and workflows, computing and storage resources and personnel for development and user support. The resulting basic service portfolio can cover the entire research cycle, whereby the individual service design may vary [2]. For example, among the seven services currently funded by Base4NFDI, IAM4NFDI offers technical cross-platform single sign-on solutions, while PID4NFDI draws on already existing PID technologies and focuses on their dissemination and the exploitation of the full potential of PIDs. The basic service DMP4NFDI supports researchers in the creation of data management plans (DMPs) with the potential help of Data Stewards and builds on the further development of the DMP software RDMO.

In the development process of these basic services, Service Stewards form a communication interface between the involved stakeholders, i.a. the service development teams and the NFDI consortia. One of these communication tasks is to support the bottom-up approach of NFDI by requirement engineering and the continuous analyses of needs in the

scientific communities, in order to ensure a high level of acceptance among the various target groups of the services. Therefore, their profile includes interdisciplinary expertise, complemented by focused technical knowledge (e.g. federated access, data literacy) and experience in project and service management [1]. In contrast to that, Data Stewards are often experts in a specific discipline. They usually provide project- and practice-oriented support and give researchers advice on the selection of suitable tools and services. Furthermore, they establish, implement and refine institutional research data management (RDM) concepts. However, both roles have a supporting function [3]. The three-phase service development process installed at Base4NFDI showcases numerous opportunities for collaboration between Data Stewards and Service Stewards. Particularly in the first two phases (initialisation & integration), which focus on exchange with the communities and the adoption of individual use cases, Data Stewards can be a valuable source of information for Service Stewards with their knowledge of the needs of researchers in their community, and can therefore also take on the role of a process stakeholder. In their bridging function between researchers and infrastructure, they have the expertise to identify relevant requirements. In the third phase (ramping-up-for-operation), in which a service is scaled up and rolled out NFDI-wide, they can support the dissemination of basic services by incorporating them into the local RDM concept, or even being part of the execution of a service. Conversely, Data Stewards and their institutions can profit from information on and early involvement in the development of the basic services. By actively participating in the process, they can help shape services to meet the needs of their community and even be use case partners or early adopters of a service, promoting the NFDI bottom-up approach. Continuing this

thought, the entire research data management landscape, in particular individual institutions such as universities where Data Stewards are often located, will drive and eventually benefit from the bottom-up development of the infrastructure by Base4NFDI and the use of the basic services.

In conclusion, there are several opportunities for collaboration between Data and Service Stewards. For both sides, it would offer participation in each other's fields of work, enabling mutual enrichment from the very beginning of the service development process. The practical implementation of these opportunities and the final success of the project will result from the acceptance of the basic services portfolio in the communities over the course of the project.

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Onboarding, Networking and Support for Data Stewards Implementing Basic RDM Services in FDM NDS

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FDM NDS

The Lower Saxony Research Data Management Initiative (“Landesinitiative Forschungsdatenmanagement Niedersachsen”, FDM NDS) was launched in November 2023 with the target of further developing and professionalizing the RDM at the 20 universities and universities of applied sciences in Lower Saxony. The state initiative is based on three pillars:

- The goal of Pillar 1 is to establish a central service and advisory center for Lower Saxony on all matters related to research data. This includes networking, coordination, creating and collecting materials, as well as providing advice on general questions regarding RDM, but also on subject-specific and specific questions such as legal aspects of RDM.
- Pillar 2 aims at the implementation of basic RDM services in 10 universities and universities of applied sciences. For this purpose, 10 data stewards (DS) are established and build up individual, locally necessary RDM foundations. The activities in Pillar 2 are closely linked to the work of

the Lower Saxony RDM initiative for universities of applied sciences and the work in Pillar 1.

- Pillar 3 comprises a project fund.

Situation and Measures Taken

The DS have different professional backgrounds and prior knowledge of RDM. Some start their work with very specific ideas and priorities, while others first have to find their way around the world of RDM. These differences must be taken into account in the onboarding and support measures.

Various measures are used for the onboarding, networking and support of the DS:

- Information
 - Welcome package with most important organizational information
 - Website and training materials
 - Zenodo community
 - Checklists and „survival kits“
 - (Online) trainings
 - Monthly newsletter
 - Help desk
- Communication

- Weekly online exchange of DS containing collegial support in specific challenges
- DS regulars' table („Data Steward Stammtisch“)
- E-mail distribution list
- Chat channel
- Collaboration
 - Shared cloud storage
 - List of experts in FDM NDS
 - Interactive online workshops containing discussion and decision on shared resources (e.g. common repository)

The DS find the exchange with each other particularly enriching. Common challenges and topics as well as existing expertise are quickly identified. The exchange of experiences confirms their own approach and shows them alternative courses of action and new ideas.

Data Steward Stammtisch

The Data Steward Regulars' Table is organized by the coordination team of pillar 2 and the Joint Lab Future Libraries & Research Data who both aim at connecting data stewards in Lower Saxony and therefore joined forces at the end of 2023.

Starting in June 2024, the Data Steward Regulars' Table is intended as an open exchange of experiences on an informal level where the data stewards can communicate among their peers. The concept of the regulars' table and the individual meetings are mainly carried out by the data stewards, supported by the above-mentioned organizers. Overall, the meetings are shaped by communicating challenges and needs from practice. In principle, the regulars' table is open to inviting external experts in the group in order to bring in additional perspectives and specialist knowledge, such as RDM-

professionals from TIB (Technische Informationsbibliothek, German National Library of Science and Technology), who bring in know-how from, for example, their work within NFDI4culture. To enable others to benefit from this work, the lessons learned from experiences will be shared within the RDM community.

Outlook Measures

The DS themselves contribute needs and ideas for further measures, which are taken up during development. They are very motivated and committed, which is why they should and want to actively participate in the design of the measures, e.g. as part of a needs analysis workshop. Specific measures in the nearer future might include:

- Development of a joint collection of materials and literature database
- Formation of interest groups (e.g. electronic lab book)
- Regular collegial advice (once or twice a year as required)
- Needs analysis workshop
- Lectures on generic but also subject-specific and legal RDM issues
- Development of a train-the-trainer workshop
- Establishment of a helpdesk specifically for legal RDM issues (second level support)

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Explorative interviews as means to conduct a needs analysis and develop a network of RDM pioneers within a University of Applied Sciences

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In this paper, we discuss the challenges of a newly introduced institutional data stewardship at HAWK (Hildesheim/Holzminden/Göttingen) and outline a strategy to meet these challenges. HAWK is a University of Applied Sciences with six faculties and scientific personnel of around 400 (including professors). The fields of research and study range from natural and life sciences to social work, early childhood education, and design. As a consequence, the data steward faces a highly heterogeneous target group with discipline-specific practices, conventions, research methods and vocabulary, a varying degree of research activities, and large variance of research data management (RDM) literacy. The level of awareness and familiarity with RDM vocabulary varies significantly between disciplines, but also between individual researchers. Neither a common vocabulary nor a certain level of knowledge can be safely assumed across the target group.

Therefore, the first challenge faced by the data steward is assessing the current state of RDM-practices and conducting a needs analysis. How this is best achieved strongly depends on the specific characteristics of the institution. As a first step for the RDM-requirements analysis, a qualitative approach is much more suited than quantitative methods. Open interviews and field observations (Döring, 2023, p. 194) are used to gain insights into the professional life of the target group, looking for special events and patterns of behaviour as well as for the unspoken laws and rules of the disciplines.

In explorative interviews with single or small groups of participants, the data steward introduces themselves and the concept of research data management. The consequent course of the interview is largely affected by the participating researchers.

Researchers are asked to introduce the data steward to their line of work. In addition, they are encouraged to express their needs independent of specific RDM-vocabulary. The data steward has the opportunity to ask questions and elucidate basic RDM-concepts as needed.

The interview output allows an assessment of RDM-literacy in the target group. Based on the findings, RDM training activities can be tailored to the needs of the researchers and the institution. Moreover, a common language is established between researchers and the data steward, opening the way for later use of quantitative methods, e.g., online questionnaires, for further surveys.

The other major challenge faced in a newly introduced data stewardship is the development of structures to promote RDM within the institution. Through the interviews, the data steward has the opportunity to identify potential allies among the scientific personnel: Researchers aware of the importance of RDM and potential benefits for their discipline, who are willing to take on the role of RDM "pioneers" within their faculty. The data steward cooperates closely with the "pioneers" to implement strategic RDM goals in their field of study, e.g., the

introduction of an electronic lab notebook or achieving data FAIRness. The "pioneers" provide deep discipline-specific insights during the implementation process, and provide use-cases that will be used to facilitate the introduction of new practices in their faculty.

It is anticipated that over time, exchange will not only happen through the mediation of the data steward, but also within the

network. This will facilitate a cross-disciplinary comparison of the researchers' experiences and insights regarding RDM.

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Effective Data Stewardship in Research Projects

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Introduction

Data stewardship, which involves the careful management, preservation, and sharing of research data, is vital for ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and efficiency in scientific research. However, implementing effective data stewardship practices within projects and institutions presents numerous challenges. This presentation explores the various aspects of implementing data stewardship, focusing on the hurdles encountered, the successes achieved, and the workflows and tools utilized.

The Collaborative Research Center (CRC) 1313 [1], titled "Interface-Driven Multi-Field Processes in Porous Media – Flow, Transport and Deformation," is based at the University of Stuttgart. Within this CRC, the Information Infrastructure (INF) [2] project plays a pivotal role in research data management, linking to the DaRUS [3] development team and acting as a bridge to other research data management teams from various Research groups. DaRUS, a public repository developed at the University of Stuttgart, is based on the open-source project Dataverse [4] and ensures that all datasets produced at the university of Stuttgart are published in a dedicated Dataverses, adhering to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles [5].

Challenges in Implementing Data Stewardship

Implementing data stewardship is often hampered by several hurdles. One significant barrier is the lack of substantial training in research data management (RDM) among researchers. For example, in projects like CRC1313, domain specialists require dedicated onboarding processes to become proficient in modern RDM practices. Additionally, there is often resistance to change. Researchers accustomed to their established workflows may be reluctant to adopt new standardized processes and tools, despite the potential benefits.

Standardizing workflows for recurring experiments and simulations is crucial to ensure comparability and reproducibility. Automating the upload of large datasets and the extraction of metadata requires robust application programming interfaces (APIs) and efficient tools to handle the volume and complexity of the data involved.

Infrastructure limitations are another challenge. Ensuring long-term data availability and accessibility involves setting up institutional repositories like DaRUS, which requires substantial investment in infrastructure and maintenance.

Achievements in Data Stewardship

Despite these challenges, there have been notable successes in the implementation of data stewardship. Standardizing workflows and integrating tools, including the use of Electronic Lab Notebooks such as eLabFTW [6], have been particularly effective. These tools facilitate the documentation of execution environments, ensuring reproducibility and comprehensive metadata annotation. Automating workflows and metadata extraction, especially through APIs such as Dataverse's native API and easyDataverse [7], has streamlined data handling processes, making them more efficient and less prone to errors.

Improvements in data management and accessibility have also been achieved. The implementation of the institutional data repository DaRUS has significantly enhanced the accessibility and findability of research data. Assigning Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to datasets ensures that data is publicly accessible and properly cited. Enhancements in data visualization and analysis tools have further facilitated the post-processing of research data, allowing researchers to easily compare datasets, extract specific metadata attributes, and reproduce research results.

Methodologies and Tools

Standardizing workflows for recurring experiments and simulations is essential for consistency. Some tools record detailed information about execution environments and intermediate results, facilitating comprehensive documentation and metadata annotation. Automation tools for data and metadata upload, such as Dataverse's native API and easyDataverse, have streamlined data handling processes. These tools enable the extraction and uploading of metadata alongside research data, ensuring that

datasets are well-documented and easily accessible. The implementation of automated software stacks in Open Container Initiative [8] (OCI)-compliant containers guarantees reproducibility across different computing environments, ensuring that research can be consistently replicated.

Enhancing data visualization capabilities within repositories like DaRUS allows for immediate insights without switching environments. Modular visualization tools enable researchers to filter data and create graphical representations, aiding in the interpretation and comparison of results. Regularly updating and refining data stewardship practices based on feedback and technological advancements is crucial. Engaging researchers in the process and providing continuous training ensures that data management practices evolve to meet new challenges and leverage emerging tools.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this presentation will delve into the implementation of data stewardship in research projects and institutions, addressing the complex landscape of cultural, technical, and infrastructural challenges. However, the successes achieved through standardization, automation, and continuous improvement demonstrate that effective data stewardship is attainable. By leveraging robust workflows and advanced tools, researchers can enhance the quality, accessibility, and reproducibility of their data, ultimately contributing to more transparent and impactful scientific research.

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Raising awareness for RDM: The importance of multipliers within the institution

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Professional research data management (RDM) is becoming increasingly important not only at universities but also at universities of applied sciences (UAS). On the one hand, this development is in part due to the inclusion of the responsible handling of research data in the Code of Good Scientific Practice of the German Research Foundation (DFG) and other authorities, which means that more and more third-party funding bodies require RDM. On the other hand, professional RDM allows for previously inaccessible opportunities and insights for science, society, and industry. This is because research at UAS is often practical and application-oriented, which means that the findings and results can quickly flow into different areas of society, the economy, and culture to create innovation and synergy effects. Research data at UAS therefore has yet rather underutilised scientific, cultural, and economic potential, especially in terms of its subsequent applied use. Professional RDM is essential to realise these opportunities.

Against this background, it is a particular challenge to bring RDM into practice at the institutional level and raise awareness among researchers as well as among administrative and infrastructural stakeholders. In this presentation, we will report our first steps in implementing RDM at one selected UAS. In doing so, special focus is placed on the role of voluntary multipliers within the institution. These voluntary multipliers are also referred to as

“data champions” [1] and can be considered key actors for raising awareness for RDM among researchers as their peers and can serve to complement the work of professional RDM staff (such as data stewards).

In this example, RDM was initially introduced by a colleague from the Research and Transfer Office with the support of the university leadership, which recognised RDM as strategically important. The initial situation was as follows: There was no professional RDM staff available and all efforts to establish RDM took place on a voluntary basis. The Research and Transfer Office consulted local initiatives for the promotion of RDM in higher education and an associated working group for guidance with introducing RDM into the institution.

The main strategy to raise the profile of RDM was to create a trickle-down effect by making RDM a topic of discussion in several committees of the institution, starting with the Executive Committee. This includes regular reporting about RDM and linking RDM with other current topics, e.g. the institution's digitisation strategy or establishing a repository. Furthermore, specific measures have been initiated aiming to establish structures and offers related to RDM, e.g. by involving the UAS into a current research data storage project and by submitting an application for a research grant in cooperation with other UAS aiming to strengthen RDM at the institutional level. As the previously

mentioned, this grant application has been successful and it is presently ongoing and thus enabling the UAS to employ a data steward (0,5 full-time equivalent) developing subject-specific RDM services.

Another key strategy to make RDM visible in the institution was to appoint a professorial RDM representative who was identified as an important multiplier due to their specific expertise and research interests. The professorial RDM representative fulfills this function on a voluntary basis. They can be considered a variant of a data champion as they have advanced experience related to research data and data management [2]. Resulting from this, they have a comprehensive understanding of the importance of well-planned research data management practice. They have a passion for sharing discipline-specific expertise, promote the FAIR principles and advocate for good RDM [1]. In doing so, they are an important actor to driving forward cultural change towards Open Science. They work in close collaboration with the data steward and the Research and Transfer Office and their feedback and assessment has been crucial to improving RDM services. As a long-standing professor, they are well known at the institution and enjoy the necessary trust of their colleagues and thus serves as a low-threshold contact person for all their questions related to RDM.

Up to now only few researchers have acquired sufficient skills and resources to

serve as multipliers for RDM. As current digitization schemes and funders' RDM guidelines and last but not least local RDM policies and services, however, serve to increase the move toward more RDM-affinity among staff, we expect that RDM awareness and skills among researchers will improve. A next step, building on the data champion definition [2], is to extend the approach of appointing a professorial RDM representative by building a collaborative and researcher-led community to drive the adoption of good RDM within their respective institutions and departments in order to contribute to the development of subject-specific RDM guidelines. This is aimed at maximising practical benefit to professors and researchers who, especially at UAS, often lack time and resources and are dependent on readily available, functional tools and guidance.

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Data stewards for the health-related sciences: Implementing RDM support at universities of applied sciences (UAS)

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Although awareness of and demand for research data management (RDM) has increased significantly in all academic fields, progress in the introduction of RDM varies greatly between disciplines. RDM seems yet underdeveloped in health-related sciences such as physiotherapy or nursing sciences. These disciplines are frequently found at universities of applied sciences (UAS), which often lack formalised RDM structures. Researchers in these areas are often unaware of the necessities of RDM [1], partly due to lack of awareness, resources, and subject-specific guidelines. At the same time, data collected in health-related sciences often include

sensitive personal data, which require particularly careful planning of data collection, processing, and storage. Overall, there is a high demand for individual support as well as for training formats to promote data literacy in health-related sciences. Establishing data stewards as points of contact for RDM on-site could significantly improve the situation described above for health-related sciences at UAS.

This poster presents a specific approach how to establish data stewards for health-related sciences at UAS which is currently being developed as part of the research

project “GesundFDM”. Particular emphasis will be placed on tasks that are essential in order to provide subject-specific RDM-support, taking into account the reality of limited resources. As the implementation process in our project is well underway, we will also share our experiences of introducing subject-specific data stewards, including hurdles and lessons learned. The idea of the presented approach is to implement local subject-specific RDM-support at selected UAS aiming to establish RDM at an institutional level. To achieve this, one data steward per UAS (0,5 full-time equivalent each) has been employed. The data stewards are employed on a temporary basis for three years corresponding to the duration of the project. Within the scope of this project, our approach is currently being tested at two German UAS, which previously had no RDM staff.

In order to implement RDM in the institution or department, the data stewards take on several roles in the project: Overseeing the integration of RDM in institutional structures, processes and policies, raising awareness for RDM and FAIR data among researchers, offering individual RDM support and training, and networking between key multipliers both within and outside their institution. Moreover, our data stewards serve as liaisons between administrative, technical, and research personnel. In doing so, they mediate or translate between the different stakeholders, who often hold very different perspectives regarding research data and frequently pursue different objectives [2]. Since our data stewards provide subject-specific advice and support, they can be viewed as *embedded* data stewards [3].

Reflecting our experience gained from the project, data stewards are essential for health-related sciences to support the current culture change towards Open Science. They serve to support the often

heavily burdened researchers in adopting good RDM. There is no universal solution how to implement data stewards that works in all contexts. Instead, each institution needs to define an individual strategy fitting its structures, resources, priorities, and goals. However, we identified several essential tasks for data stewards in facilitating RDM that might serve as inspiration for other institutions.

Creating internal visibility for data stewards and RDM support is key. Contact with researchers, particularly with internal multipliers, must be maintained in the long term. This is also the basis for understanding the researchers’ needs and understanding non-formalised approaches and practices in relation to RDM, which enable data stewards to offer tailored solutions. The ultimate goal should always be to make processes simpler for the researchers. To this end, it is important to translate generic approaches and guidelines into concrete, subject-specific recommendations and actions, tailored as closely as possible to the needs of researchers. However, it is crucial to communicate the limits of individual RDM support clearly. In our case, service focuses on providing support for researchers and enabling them to make appropriate decisions and develop adequate strategies by guiding them to adopt good RDM. In addition, cross-institutional exchange with other data stewards is important, as this allows synergies to be utilised in the best possible way and to learn from peers. What data stewards cannot do, in our case, is actively manage or curate research data for researchers.

Overall, change is slow and patience is needed to establish RDM at an institutional level and, most importantly, in the minds and practices of researchers. Clearly, need for RDM supports is substantial and will persist long-term. As a result, most of the

work that data stewards undertake is of a permanent nature. This raises the question of how services and processes that are currently being established can be maintained and made sustainable permanently. The approach of establishing local data stewards at UAS has some advantages, as researchers need a local contact person that they are familiar with and can reach easily. At the same time, local data stewards are able to gain deep insights into researchers' RDM needs. Establishing at least one data steward per institution, as recommended in this approach, can be seen as a first important step towards institutionalising RDM at UAS.

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Catalysts for Spark Igniting Research Data Management?

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A piece of charcoal lying around is unlikely to ignite by itself, even though its combustion to form carbon dioxide with atmospheric oxygen is thermodynamically favourable. A spark is required to initiate the reaction. Once the fire is ignited, raw materials can be transformed into more complex products, allowing, for example, a cheerful barbeque. Research data management should be such a cheerful BBQ, where raw data is transformed into something more insightful. Documenting the raw materials and processes involved is indispensable to reproducing the BBQ on other occasions and even having more cheerful barbeques in the future.

A vital issue in convincing researchers to use RDM tools is that most solutions that should act as a spark are rather complex, costly and complicated to implement, and the benefits of their implementation are unclear to them. Furthermore, the vocabulary and concepts used by tutors might not be meaningful or too technical to those who are taught. Finally, solutions might not be readily available for specific subjects of investigation.

Some of these issues made us think about our own solutions to organize research data in the first place. The approach was founded on the idea of creating a database from data specific to our field of research (electrochemistry and -catalysis). Here, we (echemdb developers[1]) created a tool to extract data from the literature (svgdigitizer)[2], which stores the data in a frictionless data package.[3] We also developed a metadata schema for the electrochemical data, which did not yet exist.[4] These data can be explored, visualized, and modified using the

unitpackage API.[5] Finally, the data was displayed using web development modules like MKDOCS or Jupyter Book.[6,7]

The tools developed within the frame of that project were then modified so that they are also applicable to data other than electrochemistry. Also, they can be used to annotate, explore, and display data created from experiments or simulations. A key advantage is that all tools can be used in a Jupyter environment, which is currently one of the most famous tools for such tasks.

The central part of the contribution will be about the challenges associated with creating a cheerful RDM-BBQ, finding convincing arguments, and, specifically, focusing on finding the right approach to teaching RDM solutions to “beginners” who are very eager to implement RDM workflows in their fields of research.

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Data Stewardship in the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

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Data stewardship requires an efficient data management infrastructure. The goal of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) [1] is to create and advance a comprehensive and sustainable infrastructure for research data management (RDM) that supports researchers and data stewards in the efficient management of their research data. Following the FAIR principles, data will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable to ensure its optimal use for science and society. This will increase the efficiency of the entire scientific system.

NFDI is organized as a decentralized network of competencies and services. 26 NFDI consortia, which are associations of institutions within a research area, create services tailored to their communities. In the NFDI sections, the consortia and additional partners work together on cross-disciplinary solutions that are relevant to all disciplines. The NFDI association is the umbrella organisation in which the consortia and sections work together on the common goal of a coordinated and networked research data infrastructure. The NFDI association cooperates with other national and international initiatives such as the RDM initiatives of the German federal states, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA).

Data stewards play a key role in the emerging research data infrastructure as they are experts in the complex and evolving RDM landscape by supporting

researchers, collecting and translating users' needs to service providers, advising policy makers and overall connecting all relevant stakeholders in the complex network of RDM.

Data stewards support researchers by helpdesks, trainings, consulting on complex issues, or even as embedded data managers in research projects. The focus can range from generic RDM topics to highly disciplinary topics and interdisciplinary, cooperative research. In NFDI, the working group RDM Support Network [2] is working on connecting the disciplinary helpdesks of the NFDI consortia with institutional helpdesk of the universities, of non-university research institutions, of federal state RDM initiatives, of data centres and of EOSC. This network efficiently combines the competencies of all RDM networks, and enables combined consultations of several helpdesks for complex cases. It will also offer signpost-functionality to connect users with the helpdesk which is best suited for their request. In addition, a central knowledge base that is collaboratively created by all helpdesks, will be available for all helpdesk personnel.

NFDI is science-led and needs-oriented. It is essential that the needs of the scientific community are identified and met by the services developed and provided by NFDI. Many methods are used to achieve this, ranging from surveys and interviews over community workshops and focus groups. This enables the use of agile methods with

continuous user feedback. As experts in RDM, data stewards have a comprehensive overview and deep insights into the needs of the researchers and the data that researchers create and require. The data stewards' expertise and input therefore efficiently steer the development of services in NFDI.

Efficient and reliable RDM requires governance, policies, structured processes, standards, and best practices for data management at the institutional, national, and international level, as well as disciplinary and interdisciplinary views. Data stewards are best suited to guide the process of creating these and connecting institutional policies and processes with the overarching ones created within NFDI.

To achieve widespread adoption of NFDI services and standards, data stewards are needed as ambassadors to promote and disseminate them. Data stewards can act as intermediaries between NFDI, researchers, local institutions, and other stakeholders to increase awareness and adoption of NFDI services. As a result, they strengthen the commitment of institutions to services and standards provided by NFDI. With a community of data stewards acting as multipliers, NFDI issues can be disseminated locally and data stewards in universities can be empowered to make effective use of RDM services and the new research opportunities they create.

To ensure a sustainable rdm support network, data stewards need a consolidated job-profile, job security, long-term career paths and a full range of trainings and professional education programmes. NFDI offers discipline-specific and topic-centred RDM training and workshops for both researchers and data stewards. The NFDI section Training & Education [3] contributes to refining the RDM competency matrix [4] that defines the canon of RDM competencies required at different levels, including data stewards

as the highest level. In addition, a proposal for a comprehensive NFDI basic service for RDM trainings is currently under review. This includes a workshop series and a summer school for training data stewards and a certificate course for data stewards, based on the established Certificate Course Research Data Management by ZB MED, TH Köln and fdm.nrw [5]

Strengthening and expanding the network of data stewards is recognized as a key factor for the success of NFDI. This requires sharpening the role of data stewards, supporting their work by effective services and standards, and institutionalizing sustainable structures of collaboration at national and international levels to create a vibrant community of data stewards.

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Uniting Metadata, Data, and Software Repositories in Contemporary Research Workflows

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In modern science, data management plays a central role. The rapid progress in numerous research fields has led to an exponential increase in the volume of data generated. This data must be efficiently managed, archived, and made accessible to ensure the reproducibility of results and the reuse of data. A solid data management strategy is therefore essential to ensure the quality and integrity of scientific work and to promote collaboration across different disciplines.

Adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) [1] is crucial in this context. These principles aim to improve the findability and accessibility of data, promote interoperability between different systems and disciplines, and maximize the reusability of data. By implementing these principles, research institutions can ensure that their data remains valuable and usable not only today but also in the future.

The Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR) has been working for some time on establishing and expanding a coherent, cross-disciplinary data ecosystem to support good research data management in the long term. The overarching aim of this system is to optimally support scientists at the HZDR in the management of their research data throughout its entire life cycle in order to ensure the high quality of research results in terms of maximum traceability and usability and in compliance with the FAIR principles.

The center has established comprehensive data [2] and software policies [3], supported by a proposal management system called GATE and a powerful computing center for research infrastructures. The Helmholtz GitLab instance Codebase [4], and an electronic Labbook are central tools for the development and documentation of research software and data. Long-term archiving and the sharing of research data are made possible by the tape archive and the RODARE repository [5] in accordance with FAIR principles.

All of these services and tools can also be flexibly combined via the overarching HELIPORT system [6], depending on the design of the relevant project, to create a user-controlled workflow that records all process-related data processing steps as metadata and thus makes the entire data genesis findable, machine-readable, and traceable via automatic annotation with persistent handles. An important component here is also an HZDR instance of RDMO [7], which is available for research data-related project management and data management planning.

In the constantly expanding landscape of (research) data management, it is often a great challenge for researchers to find their way through the variety of metadata catalogues such as SciCat [8], data publications on repositories based on Invenio-based repositories, or internal archives.

The major challenge currently facing very heterogeneously organized and multidisciplinary research centers and universities is the tagging of research data with standardized, discipline-specific metadata and their mutual merging or linking. Discipline-specific standard formats for metadata labeling are still too rare, which is why metadata should describe the same context but differ significantly in their form, increasingly requiring ontologies, semantic links, and knowledge graphs. The current incompatible metadata formats as a whole often look like a shattered mosaic, making it difficult for third parties to reuse research data.

However, with the appropriate strategies, this data mosaic can be effectively combined and presented to unleash its full potential. The solution currently being implemented is called SciCat. SciCat is operated at the HZDR as a pure metadata repository, which can centrally merge metadata generated during experiments, large-scale experiments, or simulations and collected in electronic lab notebooks or other recording tools by embedding detector and experiment infrastructures in automated workflow management pipelines.

In SciCat, users can then annotate the centralized project metadata with additional, rich metadata and structure it in user-customizable hierarchies. The resulting SciCat datasets can be added to projects and workflows in HELIPORT and then archived for the long term together with the associated process metadata and research data in the internal HZDR archive or linked directly as a publication with the associated research dataset in the publication repository RODARE. There are also plans to publish metadata-only records in RODARE, which would leave the research data itself in the archive or on distributed file systems but make it accessible on request in accordance with

the FAIR principles and the data management tool HELIPORT. In addition to the technical expansion of the ecosystem and the (meta)data infrastructure, great efforts are being made at the HZDR to ensure the reusability of research data while at the same time freeing researchers as much as possible from bureaucratic and additional work in research data management. The services begin with support for data management and difficult questions such as "Where does research data begin and where does metadata end?", include advice on licensing issues and support for the collection, archiving, and publication of research (meta)data, and do not end at least with technical support and often customized IT service applications.

The generic data management solutions developed at the HZDR enable a high degree of traceability and reusability and can serve as an example for other research institutions and universities in extending their own data lifecycles.

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